

Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviours towards water-smart solutions

Deliverable 5.4

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D5.4

Summary

This report of Work Package 5 – Society, Governance, Policy corresponds to “D5.4 - Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviours towards water-smart solutions (M36). It is one of the outputs from Task 5.3 - Assessment of stakeholders’ attitudes towards water-smart solutions, which aims at analysing perceptions, practices, and attitudes throughout the Project. It aims at a preliminary analysis of results from the CoP meetings and stakeholder interviews regarding issues of acceptance of water-smart solutions by policymakers, stakeholders, end-users, and the public.

The report applied the social acceptance analytical model, developed in the project’s Milestone 7 document (July 2021). Among other key concepts, it considers risk perceptions, justice and fairness notions, and trust between stakeholders, in authorities and companies. D5.4 is a preliminary report, of which there will be a final version in M48 of the project.

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04/01/2024	<p data-bbox="403 331 542 369">Version 2:</p> <ul data-bbox="403 398 1412 1097" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="403 398 1412 504">• The introductory review (chapter 1) was enriched with additional references on water reuse and water smart meters (pp. 19, 23 and 24). <li data-bbox="403 510 1412 616">• A new section summarising the key learnings from the literature review has been added at the end of the introductory chapter (section 1.5, p. 29) <li data-bbox="403 622 1412 795">• Living Lab Flanders – Note added on comments from the CoP meetings cited on Table of p. 57 under the topic ‘Trust and Justice’. Tables (section 3.4, pp. 57-60) were revised to clear repetitions. A new paragraph was added explaining how the financing was addressed at the CoP meetings among other topics (pp. 56 to 57). <li data-bbox="403 801 1412 907">• Living Lab Lisbon – Passage on consumers’ trust and water quality revised on p. 67 to improve clarity (First paragraph under ‘Trust between citizen and institutions’). <li data-bbox="403 913 1412 1019">• Living Lab Venice - Two paragraphs added on pp. 70-71 providing more information on the attitudes of stakeholders regarding the solutions of the LL. <li data-bbox="403 1025 1412 1097">• Structure of the Living Lab chapters harmonised, some sub-headings of section 3 reorganised and edited.

Table of contents

List of Figures	7
List of Tables.....	8
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations.....	9
Executive summary	10
1 Social acceptance of water-smart solutions.....	12
1.1 Water reuse.....	16
1.2 Digital tools: smart metering and decision platforms	22
1.3 Other models of acceptance for water-smart solutions	24
1.4 B-WaterSmart model of acceptance	26
1.5 Key learnings for acceptance of water innovation	30
2 Methodology	32
3 Key acceptance issues for B-WaterSmart LLs	36
3.1 Alicante	36
3.1.1 Risk perceptions.....	40
3.1.2 Notions of justice	40
3.1.3 Attitudes towards water-smart solutions	41
3.1.4 Other issues: COVID-19 and gender	42
3.2 Bodø.....	44
3.2.1 Risk perceptions.....	44
3.2.2 Notions of justice	44
3.2.3 Attitudes	45
3.3. East Frisia	47
3.3.1.Context, scope and methodology of assessing social acceptance.....	47
3.3.2.Acceptance of the Short-Term Demand Forecast Tool	47
3.3.3.Acceptance of the re-use of process water in the dairy industry	52
3.4. LL Flanders	56
3.4.1.Key issues of social acceptance	56
3.4.2.Insights from stakeholder interviews.....	60
3.5. Lisbon.....	64
3.5.1.Risk perceptions.....	65
3.5.2.Trust.....	65
3.5.3.Notions of justice	66
3.5.4.Attitudes	67
3.6. Venice	68
3.6.1.Key issues of social acceptance	68
3.6.2.Insights from the CoP meetings.....	69
4. Conclusions and next steps	73

4.1. Risk perceptions	74
4.2. Notions of justice	75
4.3. Trust	76
4.4. Implications of COVID-19 and gender issues	78
References	80

List of Figures

Figure 1 - The triangle of social acceptance.....	13
Figure 2 - Social acceptance conceptual framework.....	14
Figure 3 - Summary of the predictors of public acceptance of recycled water	18
Figure 4 - Conceptual model for the assessment of acceptance in B-WaterSmart .	28

List of Tables

Table 1 – Key components of the social acceptance model.....	34
Table 2 - Observations on social acceptance from 1st and 2nd CoP meeting	37
Table 3 - Observations on social acceptance from the 3rd CoP meeting	38
Table 4 - Observations on social acceptance from CoP meetings	57
Table 5 - B-WaterSmart acceptance model applied to Venice LL solutions	70
Table 6 - Summary of key issues of social acceptance at the B-WaterSmart LLs...	73

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CE Circular Economy

CoP Communities of Practice

DMP Drought Management Plan

DSS Decision support system

EC European Commission

EEA Environmental European Agency

EU European Union

LL Living Labs

MED Mediterranean

NBS Nature-based solution

SA Social acceptance

SDG Sustainable Development Goals

SM Smart Meters

SRL Societal Readiness Level

TRL Technology Readiness Level

WTP Willingness to Pay

UNFCCC United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UWOT Urban Water Optioneering Tool

Executive summary

D5.4 – Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviours towards water-smart solutions aims to offer a first assessment of the issues that might constitute barriers, or drivers, for the acceptance of the B-WaterSmart solutions across the socio-political, market and community target publics. The information herein collected draws from the meetings of Communities of Practice and, in some cases, is complemented by interviews with key stakeholders.

The methodology followed in this report was discussed and refined with the WP5 team members at the monthly meetings held from February to June 2023. It includes notes from the meetings of the Communities of Practice in each LL – the main point of interaction with key stakeholders – as well as interviews, which served to complement the information on the key issues of acceptance, especially in those cases where the discussions taking place at the CoPs had not yet addressed the topic extensively.

The LL solutions (technologies and tools) considered for this analysis of social acceptance were selected according to the criteria discussed between the LLs and the WP5 team. Only those most relevant and which implementation and replication will likely raise more issues were contemplated. This selection also benefited from previous work carried out to identify drivers and barriers for the implementation of the solutions, as well as socio-economic metrics for the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework (Task 5.2). The main documents for reference in this context are [D5.2. – Socioeconomic metrics for the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework](#) and [D5.3 – Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions Across 6 Cases: Policy and Governance](#).

Drawing from the MS7 analytical model (figure 4) and the MS18 report (August 2022, confidential to the consortium), we compiled selected dimensions for this preliminary assessment:

- **Risk perceptions** – Type of positions manifested during meetings regarding this solution – e.g., notions of water scarcity; possible risks to public health resulting from the solution (e.g., water reuse);
- **Attitudes** – Level of acceptability and manifested intention to adopt the solution, by these target groups;
- **Trust and Justice** – Type of positions manifested during meetings regarding (1) trust in management authorities and water utilities; (2) notions of fairness on, for instance, information transparency, accessibility, and affordability.

D5.4 includes a brief review of acceptance models in the fields of sustainability – mainly energy and water management (sections 1 and 2) and a dedicated chapter with a more detailed assessment for each of our Living Labs (LLs) – Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, and Venice. This preliminary assessment will help build new instruments for data collection over the last stage of the project, in which we will consider the inputs of D5.4 of multiple dimensions of acceptability.

For solutions related to water reuse, it is clear that there is a wide acceptability, yet it mostly stands for non-potable uses, and acceptance decreases in direct proportion with proximity to the reclaimed water. The perception of reclaimed water as 'waste' may constitute a barrier for acceptability for use in the food chain, for example, as people tend to associate process water with a waste product. Such considerations will have to be considered in future communication campaigns and citizen engagement actions.

Trust in water utilities and public institutions has also emerged as a key factor for acceptance of e.g., water reuse, namely trust in water utilities, the quality of water treatment and the safety procedures employed. Any further control over consumption that is deemed to affect consumer tariffs has to be communicated with great care and transparency, as recent surveys reveal that willingness to pay more for water services is rather limited, although these varies between regions and according to socio-economic context and perceived risk of scarcity.

Regarding notions of justice, transparent and effective public participation is paramount to ensuring procedural justice in decisions related to water management and distribution. This is especially relevant as climate change increases the frequency and intensity of future droughts, increasing the risk of water scarcity and trade-offs between economic sectors such as industry, agriculture, and tourism. To properly address issues of redistributive justice between sectors there will be the need for co-responsibility and share of costs-benefits across the key sectors that will be target of these new resources.

These were elaborated by the WP5 team members in collaboration with the LL owners and mentors. Per request of the European Commission, we have also addressed the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the consideration of gender issues in our LLs.

The next iteration of D5.4 is a final report on the acceptance of the water-smart solutions, which is to be submitted at the end of the Project, in Month 48 (August 2024) as deliverable D5.7.

1 Social acceptance of water-smart solutions

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The social acceptance of technologies in several domains (e.g., energy, water, materials) is crucial for their successful introduction in society. Although various studies have assessed social and/or public acceptance of various technologies (e.g., wind energy, carbon capture and storage, hydrogen stations, smart grids, nuclear power plants, reclaimed water reuse, smart meters, recycled materials), most studies focused on a limited set of factors that can influence acceptance, and were not based nor oriented according to a robust and comprehensive conceptual framework that addresses the key factors influencing acceptance, as well as relations between them.

The work of Wüstenhagen *et al.* (2007) and Huijts *et al.* (2012) in the field of energy provides useful insight into the framework that guides the assessment of social acceptance towards the technologies and tools to be developed across the six B-WaterSmart Living Labs.

Social acceptance: “a favourable or positive response (including attitude, intention, behaviour and – where appropriate – use) relating to a proposed or in situ technology or socio-technical system, by members of a given social unit (country or region, community or town and household, organization)” (Upham, Oltra, & Boso, 2015)

However, before discussing the conceptual framework of these authors, it is helpful to isolate the three main instances of our social acceptance assessment:

1. the focus of acceptance (e.g., technology, facility, infrastructure)
2. the concepts behind the intention and/or behaviour of acceptance
3. the actors involved with introducing and using the technology, i.e., the target groups of acceptance (e.g., citizens, consumers, farmers, policy- and decision-makers, other stakeholders).

It is worth noting that Wüstenhagen and colleagues' proposal, while providing an interesting understanding of the types of acceptance - namely socio-political, community and market acceptance (Figure 1), does not provide a clear and robust framework, as some instances of the model are placed at the same level of the acceptance process. Therefore, this model is particularly considered when defining the key actors involved in issues of social acceptance, rather than the concepts behind it.

Figure 1 - The triangle of social acceptance
(Wüstenhagen *et al.*, 2007)

More recently, the Huijts *et al.* model (2012) (Figure 2) has focused on the social and psychological factors that influence attitudes (acceptability) and behaviour (acceptance) towards the adoption of new sustainable technologies, as well as the causal relationships between these factors, and clarifies direct, indirect, or moderating effects on social acceptance. Although the relevance of the factors in the model is supported by empirical research from the energy field, the framework can be used for other technologies, namely water smart technologies and products.

The model aims to explain the intention to act in favour or against new technologies, which is assumed to be influenced by attitudes, social norms, perceived behavioural control, and personal norms. In the framework, attitude is influenced by the perceived costs, risks and benefits, positive and negative feelings in response to the technology, trust, procedural fairness (e.g., how costs and benefits are shared), procedural justice (e.g., fair decision-making process giving all relevant stakeholders an opportunity to participate). Personal beliefs are influenced by perceived costs, risks and benefits, outcome efficacy and awareness of adverse consequences of not accepting the new technology.

Huijts's model shows how attitudes, social norms, perceived behavioural control, and personal norms impact one's decision to support or oppose new technology. The perceived

costs, risks, benefits, positive and negative affective reactions towards technology, trust, procedural justice, and distributive fairness all impact attitude in the framework. Perceived costs, risks, and benefits, as well as outcome efficacy and knowledge of the negative implications of not embracing the new technology, all affect personal norms.

Figure 2 - Social acceptance conceptual framework
(adapted from Huijts et al., 2012)

The study of social acceptance towards innovations in sustainability has focused mainly on the response of local communities to the installation of renewable energy infrastructures. Over the last few decades, different disciplines within the social sciences have approached the subject using multiple, not harmonised, terminologies, such as public acceptance, whose study emerged in the 1980s. Wolsink (2018) notes that there has been a tendency to conflate social with public acceptance. He states though social acceptance should also address institutions and their processes of change, not just the public as citizens or consumers, but multiple actors and groups within society.

A particular feature of community acceptance is that it has a time dimension; before, during, and after a project follows a U-curve, going from high acceptance to (relatively) low acceptance during the setting-up phase and back up to a higher level of acceptance once a project is up and running. Empirical research on energy technologies has often verified an increasing acceptance over time, which is also supported by recent reviews on the acceptance of water-smart technologies when these technologies and systems are designed and implemented considering the needs and concerns of the local community. However, there is still a gap in the literature in terms of longer-term longitudinal studies that can document this evolution over time, with respect for instance, to water reuse (Smith *et al.*,

2018). This may be at least partially explained by an initial low level of awareness and/or knowledge of the technology (literacy) (Upham *et al.*, 2015).

Upham *et al.* (2015) have developed a comprehensive, “cross-paradigmatic” analytical framework, bridging the sociological and psychological perspectives on social acceptance. They identify five main perspectives on the acceptance of energy technologies, associated with the disciplines of economics; sociology, human geography; social psychology; cultural theory; and ‘frameworks and methods-driven work’. The authors then proceed to offer three general principles relating to social acceptance: 1) that the social acceptance of technology can be analysed at the macro, meso, and micro levels (e.g., country, community, or individual/organisation); 2) that social acceptance at these levels can refer to different ‘actor groups’, such as consumer or citizen acceptance (i.e., public), stakeholder acceptance (with formal political objectives and an interest in the outcome), or political acceptance (e.g., policy support); and 3) individual acceptance, composed of “attitudinal elements, behavioural intentions and actual behaviours” (viz., acceptance entails both feelings towards and willingness to use or adopt energy technology).

Following calls from authors such as Devine-Wright (2005), the literature has recently moved towards exploring substantial explanations for social perceptions of technologies or sustainable solutions, rather than just describing them, also increasingly accounting for the influence of one’s social networks, communities of interest and the media.

Within the study of acceptance, the analysis of social perceptions also requires an understanding of the underlying issues and conflicts of environmental justice, namely distributional justice (access to natural resources, sharing of benefits and costs), and procedural justice (participation of the stakeholders and community, including the most vulnerable social groups, in decision-making processes), fostering the development of trust within the community and towards public institutions or companies (such as water utilities). Different community sections are likely to be influenced by different aspects of justice depending on their relative position, namely by outcome fairness, outcome favourability and process fairness (Gross, 2007).

Devine-Wright (2005) also called for a stronger interdisciplinarity in the study of social acceptance, through an “integrated, multidimensional framework to guide future work” that is more grounded in established social science conceptual and methodological approaches.

Although there has been an increasing body of interdisciplinary work, Gaede, and Rowlands (2018) have noted a recent shift in influence from social acceptance as a political issue to social acceptance as a psychological issue, which raises concerns over the de-politicization of acceptance issues. Moreover, a multiplicity of research designs and methods to assess acceptance have been employed by different disciplines across fields, which results in a fragmented body of knowledge whose results may be difficult to compare. Upham *et al.* (2015) provide an extensive review of qualitative and quantitative methods that have been employed to analyse social acceptance – especially public and end-user acceptance in European countries – since the late 1990s.

It is therefore necessary to analyse the socio-economic dimensions that will be particularly relevant for the water-smart solutions under development by B-WaterSmart Living Labs, including water reuse for non-potable applications, such as watering green areas and irrigation in agriculture. Social acceptance has recurrently been cited as a key barrier for the adoption of alternative and innovative solutions in water management (Lazarova *et al.*, 2013). While contextual factors such as physical proximity have proved crucial for social acceptance of renewable energy infrastructures, e.g., wind energy farms, others will emerge as more relevant for water-smart solutions.

Furthermore, extensive work has been done on thematic areas that are most relevant for B-WaterSmart, notably water reuse. Smith *et al.* (2018) have reviewed the most recent literature in this field, published since the early 2000s, and observe how multiple strands of literature have been emerging and becoming more sophisticated in their understanding of the process of 'legitimation' of water technology within society.

1.1 Water reuse

Water reuse has a long tradition of successful implementation in countries like Israel, California, Australia, China, and Thailand, but so far it has had a limited application in Europe. Little awareness of the potential benefits among stakeholders and the public and the lack of a supportive and coherent framework for water reuse have been pointed out as significant barriers preventing a wider spreading of this practice across the EU (Fielding *et al.*, 2019).

Although the potential role of reclaimed water as an alternative source of water supply is now well acknowledged and embedded within international, EU and national strategies, at present, only about 1 billion cubic meters of treated urban wastewater are reused annually, which accounts for approximately 2.4% of the treated effluents and less than 0.5% of the annual EU freshwater withdrawals. This shows that the EU potential is much higher, estimated at 6 billion cubic metres – six times the current volume. Southern Member States such as Spain, Italy, Greece, Malta and Cyprus and northern Member States like Belgium and Germany already have numerous initiatives regarding water reuse for irrigation, industrial purposes, and aquifer recharge in place. Cyprus and Malta already reuse more than 90% and 60% of their water, respectively, while Greece, Italy, and Spain reuse between 5 and 12% of their effluents, indicating a vast potential for further uptake.

Reusing water can provide significant environmental, social, and economic benefits while contributing to the broader water sector, a key component of a circular economy. Moreover, compared to alternative water supply sources, such as desalination or water transfers, water reuse often requires lower investment costs and energy, contributing to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Water reuse also encompasses significant potential in the creation of green jobs in the water-related industry, and it is estimated that a 1% increase in the growth rate of the water industry in Europe could create up to 20 000 new jobs.

Water reuse is one of the key focus of the B-WaterSmart LLs, aiming at contributing to significantly increase the rates of reuse at local or regional level - percentages of water reuse at the start of the project (2020) and expected at the end (2024), for each LL, in relation to water supplied. Alicante 30% (40%); Flanders (<1/2%); Lisbon (<2/5%); East Frisia (1/2%); Venice (4%/50% at local level).

Achieving efficient water allocation requires a multidisciplinary approach to managing water resources to maximise economic welfare while guaranteeing social equity and ecological sustainability (UN-Water, 2017). The UN Sustainable Development Goal on Water (SDG6) also explicitly targets a substantial increase in recycling and safe reuse globally by 2030, to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all, which is aligned with Goal 12 on sustainable consumption and production.

For these SGDs to be achieved, stakeholders and governments should be well informed about water usage and the advantages of reclaimed water, which implies an understanding of 'people's key concerns and considerations about water recycling that may provide a helpful guide to the type of expert information people are likely to seek (Fielding *et al.*, 2019).

The study of social acceptance also informs about the need to improve targeted information dissemination in line with improving water management practices in the urban context, where the goal is to gain support from the public for agency decisions (Fielding *et al.*, 2019; Hartley *et al.*, 2019; Chfadi *et al.*, 2021).

A significant amount of empirical work has been conducted to investigate the level of public acceptance of recycled water. Fielding *et al.* (2019) usefully summarised the current state of the art in a review that finds, among other things, a consistently positive relationship between acceptance and dissemination of information (e.g., about recycling processes, safety, and benefits). The authors observe this pattern across differing research methodologies, including studies based on case analyses and experiments.

Most studies investigating public acceptance of recycled water come to the same conclusion – that people are very open to using recycled water for uses with low personal contact, such as watering trees and shrubs in their garden, but are reluctant to adopt reclaimed water for uses with high personal contact, such as drinking or bathing (Fielding *et al.*, 2019; Dolnicar *et al.*, 2011). These studies commonly investigated the influence of demographics (gender, age, education, and income) and demographics of interest to water authorities (race/ethnicity, religion, and political affiliation) on public acceptance. Regardless of the measure of acceptance used, the same pattern emerges: acceptance of recycled water drops with increased human contact (Figure 3).

Some factors hypothesised to increase the level of likelihood that respondents would use recycled water are significant: (1) previous experience with water restrictions; (2) not feeling limited by water restrictions; (3) increased knowledge about recycled water; (4) more positive perceptions of recycled water; (5) a high extent of other people influencing 'one's water-related behaviours; (6) pro-environmental attitudes; (7) older age (note that the underlying model is assuming a linear relationship, so the regression results indicate that higher age is associated significantly with a higher stated likelihood of using recycled water); (8) religion not being a vital life factor; and (9) watching State (non-commercial) TV channels (Dolnicar *et al.*, 2011).

✓ **Significant findings**

Studies that found a statistically significant relationship between the proposed antecedent variable and acceptance of recycled water.

✗ **Non-significant findings**

Studies that tested the relationship between the proposed antecedent variable and acceptance of recycled water but did not find a significant association.

Figure 3 - Summary of the predictors of public acceptance of recycled water
(Source: Fielding *et al.*, 2019, p. 575)

Chen *et al.* (2013) conducted a household survey in two residential areas with dual pipes in Australia to analyse community acceptance of reclaimed water for laundry (20% of household water usage in the country). The variables most contributing to the acceptance of this new end use were: (i) positive attitude on receiving recycled water, (ii) positive opinion on the idea 'recycled water is an alternative to drinking water', (iii) increased confidence by reading from other customers or successful examples, and (iv) increased confidence, by adding a small unit to improve the water quality. Conversely, the main concerns are related to fear of potential odours and possibly higher costs.

It becomes clear that the acceptance of the multiple reuse technologies that have existed for decades is dependent not only on the advancements in the science of purification and the reduction of both the complexity and costs of treatment. The knowledge that water reuse is recognised in scientific circles, and increasingly by water utilities, as a source of clean, safe, and reliable water for residential, industrial, and agricultural purposes needs now to be transferred to end-users to overcome barriers to the adoption of potable reuse, including concerns about chemicals, pathogens, and social stigma (i.e., the 'yuck' factor) (Hartley *et al.*, 2019).

Nevertheless, it also becomes clear that studies on social acceptance of water reuse must consider differences in local water, political, environmental, and cultural contexts (Hurlimann and Dolnicar, 2016). Having surveyed public acceptance of urban stormwater reuse in Australia, Mankad *et al.* (2019) emphasise that the most important predictors of acceptance are social norms and value-driven attitudes, including perceptions of approval from significant others (e.g., family and friends) and personal moral values. Moreover, they stress that a community's perceived 'water culture' is determinant for acceptance of innovations but may sometimes have counterproductive effects. In this case, creating a new source of water was seen by some respondents as contrary to long-held national practices of water conservation.

While acknowledging the importance of improving knowledge of technologies among the public, Smith *et al.* (2018) highlight that increased literacy *per se* will not secure acceptance of water reuse (deficit model) and that other deep-rooted factors significantly shape public reactions, such as trust in water service organisations, and/or in the government agencies that oversee water services, which is supported by recent studies, such as Stotts *et al.* (2019), as well as a recent survey carried out in Lisbon (see box).

Cotzen *et al.* (2023) emphasise how an 'engaged' use (rooted in support) or 'active' use (rooted in behaviour change) are determinant for ensuring that consumers keep pro-environmental practices over time. They note that active use that requires new routines tends to drop after the initial promotion of a new technology. Therefore, both good information and convenience are crucial to ensure an effective adoption over the longer term.

As Smith *et al.* (2018) have noted in their extensive review, empirical research on public acceptance of water reuse has been gaining a better understanding of how different social, cultural, and psychological factors interplay. Having minimal contact with the reused water is not so determinant for consumers if there is trust in the water management authorities and trust in the quality of water supplied. Other factors less explored, such as awareness of unplanned (*de facto*) reuse practices, can have a more expressive influence in this context.

Persistent personal beliefs or preferences still have a strong influence. In a survey conducted in Portugal among a representative sample of the national population (Águas de Portugal, 2021), 22% of the respondents declared they did not drink tap water, although water quality standards are very high according to EU requirements. Almost half of these (48,6%) justify this option saying they dislike the "taste" of tap water, which appears to be related to a lack of trust in water quality, as the same percentage gives that reason for not drinking tap water.

A recent study on the social perspectives on desalination and water reuse in Texas, US, addressed stakeholders' positions on water alternatives, in a context of increasing water scarcity and dire predictions for shortages, through Q-methodology – a statistical method to empirically describe and analyse the subjective positions regarding a particular topic or domain – to identify how key stakeholders cluster distinct positions. The results showed that social perspectives are organised around three factors: 1) *diversification is key*, 2) *conservation before desalination*, and 3) *the private sector can do it*. *Diversification is key* refers to positions that defend that desalination and water reuse are both important components in a set of possible solutions for supporting urban water security. The factor "conservation before desalination" questions the priority given to desalination over other technologies and solutions such as conservation, water reuse, or groundwater replenishment and strongly opposes to the use of desalination to encourage additional urban or suburban growth, also being the most cautious position towards desalination. Lastly, the "private sector can do it" factor is the strongest pro-desalination social perspective and is based on statements like "[desalination] is the only drought-proof source of water" and "it's never going to rain enough in Texas" (Brannstrom *et al.*, 2022).

The case of Lisbon

In 2020 a study on Receptiveness to the Reuse of Reclaimed Water has been conducted in Lisbon (Lisboa E-Nova, 2020). It reports the result of a qualitative-quantitative research, which aims to assess the receptiveness of Lisbon's citizens to the use of treated wastewater in public outdoor spaces, also integrating the point of view of institutions and stakeholders. The report describes the work methodology used, the results and the conclusions. The sociological analysis was structured in three phases, which included the constitution of two focus groups, surveys, and individual interviews with the main stakeholders of the field in the city of Lisbon, with the contribution of several experts, decision makers and operational officers.

Among several other relevant information that can be drawn from this study, there is a high predisposition of citizens to accept the use of reclaimed water in outdoor spaces (81.4%). This significant sample is the result of spontaneous positive associations between the use of reclaimed water and aspects like the optimization of the efficiency of reclaimed use, more rationality, cost-effectiveness, and environmental protection. Moreover, the high level of public acceptability is due to the fact that:

- (i) An efficient management responds to one of the structural trends in citizens' thinking: it ensures environmental protection and preservation of natural resources;
- (ii) A growing awareness that water is a finite resource;
- (iii) A growing awareness of the consequences of water scarcity;
- (iv) The use of drinking water in public spaces is considered wasteful;
- (v) The public attributes to public entities the responsibility for stimulating water conservation practices;
- (vi) The public identifies several situations with potential application for water reuse.

Those who are less convinced about this alternative argue, above all, that they are mistrustful of this potential. Water reuse is also related to other potential negative associations, such as the incorporation of chemicals, which raises safety and health concerns. The results of the study are aligned with the literature review, in that the uses that meet more acceptance are outdoor public spaces irrigation, street washing and car washing. In another recent survey carried out in Portugal, at the national level, 59% of respondents considered that water use in public spaces has not been a good example of responsible management, thus supporting a greater receptiveness to efficiency measures (Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 2020).

Another interesting aspect of the study consists in the comparison of several analysis parameters between the general public (n=333) and the specialised public (n=296). When they are confronted for example about the advantages and disadvantages of water reuse, there are significant differences in their perceptions, which means that not always the positive perceptions of the general public are grounded on a well-founded and conscious basis. In this sense, literacy, communication, and information emerge as key elements to improve the levels of awareness regarding the urban water cycle.

Also under the same topic, a study published in 2023 examines the relation between the perception of water scarcity and the recognition of alternative water sources, specifically desalination and recycled water. A 46-item survey (n = 588) conducted in Australia shows that a higher awareness of water scarcity increases the acceptance of alternative potable water sources, specifically for recycled water, but not for desalination. The recognition of climate change mediates the association of water scarcity with encouraging the adoption of alternative potable water sources (Semasinghe, Jatrana & King, 2023).

The EU-funded project NextGen Water (2018-2022) followed two methodological approaches to study the circular economy for water: a quantitative approach using extensive surveys and a qualitative course employing in-depth interviews. In the quantitative study, three large-scale surveys to the general public in the UK, Netherlands, and Spain were conducted with more than 2500 participants. The surveys examined three theoretical concepts: willingness to use, support, and willingness to pay more for the goods derived from those circular solutions (recycled drinking water and food grown with recovered nutrients). The overall findings demonstrated strong support for both circular solutions across countries, and social norms and emotions emerged as the strongest predictors for both circular products regarding support and willingness to consume. This means that participants are more likely to support circular solutions and consume the resulting products if they feel positive about those products and if they believe that others would feel the same way. The study is grounded on legitimacy theory (cognitive, pragmatic, normative, and regulative). The La Trappe demo case's emphasis on visitors and consumers raised the branding part of the pragmatic dimension. From a theoretical position, the findings account for the further development of the legitimacy framework of social acceptance by including new features to already well-established categories (e.g., pragmatic and regulative legitimacy) (Smith *et al.*, 2023).

One of the crucial points related to the social acceptance of the proposed solutions within the scope of B-WaterSmart is the implementation and development of treated water reuse practices. The reuse rate in most of Europe is still at very low levels, although countries like Israel and Spain already have higher rates. Therefore, strategies that favour the implementation of this solution are of utmost importance for climate change adaptation.

The involvement of stakeholders, in terms of knowledge about the alternative, has been crucial for the implementation of water reuse, as well as the public's acceptance. The acceptance of the different actors promotes the development of important actions for reuse, such as the construction of reuse infrastructure and regulations that will ensure implementation. For the public, it is important to ensure the dissemination of relevant information, as well as participation in decision-making processes for reuse projects.

A recent survey carried out by the main water utility in Portugal (representative sample of the national population, 1002 respondents) shows that droughts and water scarcity are largely considered among the main consequences of climate change, and it is also among the top concerns for the respondents (after air and maritime/coastal pollution). 74,7% of the respondents reveal a very positive predisposition towards water reuse for non-potable uses; however, would be less available for such innovation if it implies a tariff increase (very positive falls down to 32,9%). The acceptance of slight tariff increases is greater in the Southern regions more affected by droughts, but lower in Lisbon (perception of more abundant water resources) (Águas de Portugal, 2021).

The scarcity of water has a significant impact on society's sense of urgency as it highlights the immediate need for action to address the situation. Water scarcity emphasises the reality that water resources are limited and need to be used more efficiently and sustainably. This shift in perspective recognises that water is not an infinite resource and measures must be taken to ensure its future availability. The awareness of this limitation generates a sense of urgency to adopt conservation practices and sustainable water management and accept

solutions such as water reuse. Another important aspect of the sense of urgency brought by scarcity is its direct impact on basic needs, affecting access to safe drinking water, sanitation, and agriculture. When people experience restrictions in accessing water, urgency to find solutions becomes a primary concern.

Water scarcity also has significant economic impacts, affecting various sectors such as agriculture, industry, and tourism. This generates additional pressure to act quickly and find solutions to minimise negative economic impacts. The sense of urgency can also promote increased awareness of climate change, since water scarcity is often linked to changing precipitation patterns and extreme events, such as severe droughts and intense rainfall. As people become more aware of the connections between water scarcity and climate change, the urgency to mitigate and adapt to the effects of these changes intensifies. Lastly, water scarcity often generates social and political pressure for governments, institutions, and leaders to take action to address the issue. When the sense of urgency is consolidated, citizens tend to mobilise, demand solutions, and expect the implementation of concrete policies and measures to ensure water security.

1.2 Digital tools: smart metering and decision platforms

In recent years, in addition to the development of innovative sources of energy and water, efficient use and smart, manageable systems have been pursued to deal with climate change issues and increased demand for resources due to rapid economic growth. Smart meters (SM) are considered a method to achieve efficiency, sustainable development, and the potential to improve the quality, reliability, and efficiency of resource supply (water and energy).

While the existing literature on smart meters tends to be dominated by research that focuses on technical aspects (e.g., potentials of the technology, use of smart meters to provide feedback to consumers and to tailor efficient use behaviours), more recent quantitative and qualitative research has explored consumer attitudes toward smart and innovative technologies in both water (e.g., the influence of feedback and tailored information on modelling water use conservation and efficiency behaviours) and energy sectors (e.g., smart meters and smart grids), where social scientists have looked at some of the challenges that need to be addressed, such as public resistance or lack of acceptance towards the installation of this technology, both in terms of the application of this technology in the water sector and in the energy sector, with more research done in the latter topic.

As noted above, much of the research on the social acceptance of smart and innovative technologies in the energy sector (Bugden & Stedman, 2019; Chou et al., 2015; Cominola et al., 2015; Raimi & Carrico, 2016) has produced significant knowledge, conceptual approaches and methods that can be successfully transferred and applied to comparatively under-studied sectors such as water (Cominola *et al.*, 2015).

The challenges of actually deploying a large-scale, high-resolution metering network in the real world, such as privacy issues, beliefs, risks perception and attitudes, are being considered both in the European Union (Barnicoat & Danson, 2015; Buchanan *et al.*, 2016; Chawla *et al.*, 2020; Kaufmann *et al.*, 2013) and worldwide.

One of the most relevant issues deriving from the literature regarding the acceptance of smart meters is household privacy and data security about detailed water use information conveyed by this technology (Cominola *et al.*, 2015), raising challenges regarding consumers'

acceptance towards water supply metering and monitoring. Previous research in the UK has shown neither overwhelming support nor opposition to installing SM technology. Instead, the British public appears to be either apathetic or ambivalent about whether it should be installed. Buchanan *et al.* (2016) investigated what is required to secure household acceptance and engagement with SM. Based on the results of four deliberative focus groups (n=24) to explore consumer perceptions of smart meters, the findings suggest that participants were able to identify both threats (e.g., loss of autonomy/control, privacy concerns, and mistrust of profit-driven energy providers and concerns about how it would affect one's own life and the lives of others) and opportunities associated with smart metering initiatives (e.g., avoiding burdensome meter readings, more accurate billing, the chance to lower bills, and enabling future smart meter services, including mobile notifications and smart controls that would allow consumers to turn off "unused" appliances remotely). Participants responded positively to an automated monitoring system that could be combined with time-of-use tariffs to save energy.

In addition to European research, studies in other parts of the world have also attempted to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the factors involved in adopting SM in different populations, mainly among consumers. Bugden and Stedman (2019) in the US examined the effect of privacy, procedural and distributive fairness, price consciousness, climate change risk perceptions, familiarity, and environmental concern on smart energy meter acceptance and engagement, through a survey with 609 households in Ithaca (NY). Results showed that familiarity, climate risk perception, and price consciousness had the most significant influence on smart meter adoption, implying that those who reported greater familiarity with the technology perceived it as a potential buffer against climate change and were more willing to adopt smart meters. The findings also have implications for communication, as this should focus on increasing familiarity (exposure to and knowledge about the benefits), demonstrating the climate benefits of smart meter-enabled products and services.

Conversely, in the US, Raimi & Carrico's (2016) research tested the influence of knowledge and perception of smart energy technology on SM adoption through an online survey with 305 participants. The results highlight that knowledge about smart technology was correlated with positive beliefs about its effects on global warming, security, and affordability and emphasise that exposure to smart technology seems to result in scepticism about the benefits of this technology rather than positive attitudes or acceptance. Although those with more contact with SM knew more about it, they saw less benefit in the technology, displayed more health concerns, and had more negative views of smart technology's effects on supply affordability than participants with less contact. The demonstrated resistance to SM may not be due to distrust of utilities *per se*, since participants preferred devices from their utility, but to suspicion of the impact of the technology itself.

Recent studies that focused specifically on the adoption of water meters reiterated some of the findings on energy SM, but also have contributed to reveal how water technologies differ. Cominola *et al.* (2021) carried out a study on smart meters installation in Spain and concluded that the ability to engage directly with a digital platform and have access and control of their own consumption data is determinant to drive water saving behaviours.

March *et al.* (2017) emphasised the need for more systematic cost-benefit analyses that take into account the social and environment benefits of water SM in specific socio-economic

settings such as tourist areas. Interviews with water managers in Alicante, Spain, raised the advantages of long-distance metering for the water utilities (e.g., saving human resources and travel), but also the importance of considering the housing dynamics of a region (e.g., second homes and seasonal occupancy).

In a UK study on smart water meters that use Internet of Things (IoT), Goulas *et al.* (2022) concluded that control of the data registered, but also free installation of the devices and the opportunity to reduce water bills were key drivers of adoption among households. The socio-economic profile was deemed determinant in this study, as homeowners, for instance, were statistically more likely (than renters) to accept that water companies would have access to their detailed consumption data.

A large-scale survey in the Netherlands (n=1037) pointed out that consumers who already owned digital energy meters are more likely to accept a digital water meter, but costs are once again a concern. They are more likely to accept a free offer (Koop *et al.*, 2021). Data privacy was a concern only for 6%, yet the authors note that these results are likely to be impacted by privacy debates that might arise in the public and media agendas over time.

Koop *et al.* (2021) also emphasised the importance of considering the values perspectives of water users when tailoring communication campaigns on water saving and metering, i.e. whether they lean towards “egalitarian and solidary” concerns (with vulnerable social groups and future generations), or instead towards sustainability or comfort advantages. An integrated policy and communication design, that considers both the values and needs of consumers (e.g., with subsidised efficiency schemes for buildings), will be necessary to ensure a fair implementation of water digital tools for both early adopters and vulnerable households (Michalec *et al.*, 2019)

1.3 Other models of acceptance for water-smart solutions

The study of social acceptance of water innovation is still emerging, along with *bottom-up* approaches in favour of greater involvement of stakeholders and the co-production of water-smart solutions. Recently, there has been a debate for the expansion of evaluation models such as Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to the social sphere. Innovation Fund Denmark has developed a 9-level scale designated Societal Readiness Levels (SRL) within the H2020 Project [New HoRRizon](#), and this has started to be applied to other H2020 research projects also in the field of water innovation, such as SCOREWater (Sanne *et al.*, 2019). If the societal readiness for the social or technical solution is expected to be low, suggestions for a realistic transition towards societal adaptation are required, such as improvement in information and further testing with the direct involvement of stakeholders. Bruno *et al.* (2020) have argued for the expansion of TRL to the legal, organisational, and societal dimensions, in order to be applied to assess the potential of new and existing digital technologies to promote innovation in European public services.

The concept of SRL as emerged as a practical approach to assessing responsible research and innovation (RRI), considering the implications of R&D actions on “shared societal objectives such as sustainable economic growth, social justice, gender, equality, and protection of human health and the environment. H2020 Project NewHoRRizon developed an evaluation tool for SLR that can be freely accessed on <https://thinkingtool.eu>. On this

platform, project managers can register and assess the performance of their actions across several entry points, from the design stage to the dissemination of results. They are prompted to answer a series of specific questions, including on what learnings has stakeholder engagement brought throughout the project, how have been gender issues been considered and what open access procedures are being followed.

The SLR 'thinking tool' aims to be a pragmatic approach to RRI in light of ensuring a broader and more effective acceptability of the solutions developed among end users and society. From a review of more than 200 articles related to RRI, the NewHoRRizon team established four main conditions for ensuring a good interaction with stakeholders and acceptability of the projects results: anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, and responsiveness. It integrates six distinct keys (public engagement, open access, science education, gender, ethics, and governance), in line with the European Commission's Eighth Framework Program for research and innovation.

While the SLR tool is a useful platform to evaluate the societal impact of projects, it is not *per se* a model of analysis of social acceptability that can orientate the collection of data among different target publics. We understand the platform is relevant mostly for an internal evaluation of projects through different stages, and therefore can be used as a complement, but not a substitute, for a conceptual model as the one developed by B-WaterSmart (Milestone 7, July 2021).

While this is the first application of the B-WaterSmart acceptance model on a public deliverable, as well as the first one with a preliminary analysis of primary data from the Living Labs of B-WaterSmart, its next iteration - the final version of this deliverable to be submitted in Month 48 (D5.7) - will contemplate a more detailed analysis and collection of additional data resorting to complementing methodologies.

Other projects resorted to the theory of legitimacy as a basis for analysing the social acceptability of water-smart solutions, as is the case of H2020 NextGen. Smith *et al.* (2023) carried out a survey for their final report on acceptability, organised around four dimensions of legitimacy (cognitive, pragmatic, normative and regulative). They analysed how the respondents perceived the project solutions desirable or appropriate within their social context, covering cases in the UK (n=1028), the Netherlands (n=751) and Spain (n=800). The surveys focused on two circular solutions utilised in the water and wastewater sector – the use of recycled water for drinking purposes, and the use of recovered nutrients to grow food - from the perspective of three dependent variables: willingness to consume, support for, willingness to pay more for the products of those circular solutions. The proportions of respondents who supported or strongly supported the use of recycled water for drinking were 67% in the UK, 73% in Spain and 75% The Netherlands. The proportions of respondents who supported or strongly supported the use of recovered nutrients to grow food were respectively 74% (UK), 75% (NL) and 85% (ES). There were significant differences in responses to water recycling and responses to recovered nutrients, with the latter having higher acceptance in all three countries and across all dependent variables.

The key conclusions from this analysis are that, for two of the dependent variables (support and willingness to consume), social norms and emotions emerged as two of the strongest predictors, for both circular products and in all three countries. This means that respondents

in all three countries are more likely to support the circular solutions, and consume the products from them, if they feel positively towards them, and if they believe that others would do the same. For the third dependent variable (willingness to pay more) the picture was more mixed. Social norms had the strongest role in predicting willingness to pay more for food grown with recovered nutrients, while knowledge had a stronger role in predicting willingness to pay more for recycled water.

In the water reuse sphere, it is commonly assumed that citizens are more likely to accept recycled water if they have direct, local experience of water scarcity. Smith *et al.* explored this assumption in our research by examining perceived challenges for water resources at different scales, and what role those perceptions had in predicting responses to circular products. Respondents were asked to state the extent to which they believed that there is a challenge for water resources on a local, national, and global level. In all three countries, respondents were more likely to agree that water resources were at risk at a global level, rather than at a national or local level. This difference was particularly apparent in the UK and the Netherlands. Respondents from Spain were significantly more likely to agree that there is a challenge for water resources at a national and local level, which is to be expected, as Spain has one of the lowest rainfall levels in Europe, suffers from water scarcity and is often hit by droughts.

As engagement activities related to circular systems in water and wastewater often focus on their local impacts and local benefits, a key recommendation emerging from NextGen is to highlight the role of circular solutions in addressing global challenges.

1.4 B-WaterSmart model of acceptance

The model for analysing social acceptance issues in B-WaterSmart was first proposed and discussed in the Milestone 7 internal report "Assessment of social acceptance and behaviour towards water-smart solutions" (Gomes *et al.*, 2021) and was further used as the main framework for analysing social acceptance issues regarding water-smart solutions produced within B-WaterSmart.

When building the model and selecting its key concepts, we also took into consideration other B-WaterSmart outputs, such as MS6 – "First long-term vision of LL owners for water-smartness in their system" - and D6.1. – "What is water-smartness and how to assess it?", and is aligned with the water-smartness definition of the project, approved in May 2021:

Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses, to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society, to boost value creation around water, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure.

Based on the review of the critical literature considering different disciplinary approaches and conceptual models, as well as on the review of the key acceptance issues raised by B-WaterSmart Living Labs, this interdisciplinary model harmonises concepts from both environmental sociology and environmental psychology and provides an analytical background that can be easily applied by a wider audience within the B-WaterSmart consortium. This model is the overarching framework for the project, yet considering that specific elements of the core (e.g., risk perceptions, willingness to pay or justice issues) will be given a different emphasis depending on the type of water-smart solution under development within the specific context of each Living Lab.

The core of the model refers to the interconnected and reciprocal influence of various psychosocial concepts such as risk perception and awareness (e.g., towards water security and safety issues), notions of fairness and trust influencing both distributive and procedural justice, social and personal norms determining attitudes towards water-smart solutions and the intention to accept/adopt water solutions. The above-referred concepts consider the influence of contextual and individual factors (Upham *et al.*, 2015) that will shape how involved actors perceive and act towards water-related challenges, policies, and technologies and are represented in the diagram as having a reciprocal influence between them (Figure 1).

At the social psychological core, the model considers eight dimensions: risk perceptions, fairness notions and trust, social and personal norms, attitudes, and the intention to adopt a given solution (i.e., acceptability).

Risk perception relates, in the light of the water challenges, to water security and safety, encompassing the awareness of water scarcity (or perception of abundance) and the impacts of climate change and extreme weather events, as well as concerns associated with the safety and health risks of reclaimed water and/or process water for different purposes (e.g., watering green areas vs agriculture irrigation vs drinking water). With the increase in digitalisation, also in the water sector, risk perceptions related to privacy concerns and data security are rising, for instance, reflected in the concerns about installing smart meters at private homes.

Figure 4 - Conceptual model for the assessment of acceptance in B-WaterSmart
(Gomes *et al.*, 2021, adapted from Huijts *et al.*, 2012; Wüstenhagen *et al.*, 2007, Upham *et al.*, 2015)

Regarding the analysis of fairness notions, two dimensions are considered: **distributive justice** and **procedural justice**. Distributive justice relates to issues of resource access, equity and distribution of costs and benefits, which ultimately (coupled with social variables such as income) will influence the willingness to pay (WTP) for technological innovation or an increased tariff. Procedural justice concerns how a decision-making process is conducted based on community engagement principles (recognition, respect, and equity) and how fair social actors consider the process has been, namely, the degree of consultation of all interested parties and what degree of influence they effectively have in the decisions and how transparent was the whole process (e.g., perceived procedural bias).

Trust is a crucial element for the understanding of social acceptance. In this context, trust (in the water utility and public authorities, for instance) can be measured by the analysis of challenges and solutions, namely, trust in how companies will manage the information provided by smart meters, for example, or trust in the authorities responsible for water treatment and safety controls. Accurate information and honest communication with stakeholders encourage shared responsibility and learning in face of environmental challenges such as climate change and water scarcity. The willingness to share power and accountability, through mechanisms of co-creation of solutions, such as the Communities of Practice, will ultimately build trust and ownership.

For the purposes of the B-WaterSmart acceptance model, we understand personal norms as the internalisation of social norms, e.g., the perceived social pressure or moral obligations to perform or not perform a given behaviour (Huijts *et al.*, 2012). This concept of personal norms derives from the models of social psychology, as cited in this report, and is used in this strict sense, with no relation to ethical or legal norms. Paired with notions of justice, relevant actors of the process of social acceptance will form and state how they perceive the value of water (again influenced by their direct experience with water sources, episodes such as droughts and their attachment to a place /environmental context and so on).

Attitudes towards water-smart innovations, i.e., evaluative judgements towards new technologies, will arise as an outcome of risk perceptions, fairness notions, social and personal norms (including personal values and beliefs influenced by social norms), consequently, lead to an intention to adopt a given technology (when it requires an active

decision, a purchase, etc.). The intention is an expression of acceptability (or lack thereof) that may lead to an effective behaviour of opposition or adoption.

The influence of contextual and individual factors on social acceptance is operated through the social networks, groups of belonging, environmental and social identity, cultural values, and the media on the perception, attitudes, and behaviours around water (e.g., from scarcity awareness to water conservation behaviours and practices to the adoption of a given technological innovation, etc.). Furthermore, place attachment, with its environmental context and history, will also determine how people perceive the value of water and the solutions adopted for its management. While in the context of energy, such as the installation of wind turbines, this can lead actors to be concerned with their proximity to these infrastructures (e.g., impacts of noise, privacy), in the water context, proximity might not be a determinant factor for acceptance, at least not with all types of solutions considered. Yet, attachment to a place/landscape will still be essential to shape perceptions and values around water.

The influence of individual background and characteristics refers to direct experiences, preferences, motivations, memories, knowledge of water issues and literacy on a given technology that can vary considerably among actors and socioeconomic groups, as well as according to social variables such as gender, age, education levels, income, ethnicity, and religion.

Finally, the model considers three types of social acceptance: **socio-political, market and community acceptance**. Socio-political acceptance is social acceptance on the broadest level concerning the acceptance/acceptability by key stakeholders and policy actors of effective policies. Community acceptance refers to the specific acceptance by local stakeholders, citizens, and local authorities. A particular feature of community acceptance is the time dimension, interfering with the acceptability of new technology, as demonstrated by empirical research on the acceptance of renewable energy projects. More prolonged exposure to technology may, among other factors, improve knowledge of its operation, impacts and benefits. The time factor may increase acceptance of innovation or, on the contrary, lead to a stronger rejection. In any case, it is a crucial variable to consider when planning a project and its communication with stakeholders and the community. The last level of acceptance refers to market acceptance, or the process of market adoption of a given innovation (technological or not) and focus on consumers/clients and investors (Wustenhagen *et al.*, 2007).

While **community acceptance** has been given the particular emphasis on the contexts of B-WaterSmart Living Labs, market acceptance is also key for the water-smart solutions (e.g., end-users and replicators of the efficient management tools in the industry), as well as the acceptance by national and regional institutions, such as regulators and environment agencies, in the socio-political sphere. Besides each of these levels, different actor groups will have to be consulted as targets to accept B-WaterSmart solutions: policymakers, local authorities, key stakeholders, end-users of each solution, and the broader public.

In B-WaterSmart, **socio-political acceptance** is being addressed through specific focus groups in the CoPs and also other ongoing work under WP5: T5.4 (Guidelines and Recommendations for Policy and Regulations, ongoing until M48) and D5.5. (submitted August 2023); submission of guidelines and recommendations for policy & regulation D5.6 & D5.8 – report and set of policy briefs for different topics and target groups; focus groups with

policy-makers within CoPs. **Market acceptance** is mostly addressed through T7.3 - Exploitation and route to market.

The plan for interaction and validation of the acceptance issues has been discussed by WP1 and WP5 team members and is part of Task 5.3 (from which D5.4 draws) and has been considered in the design of the CoP Roadmaps, with the calendar of meeting and focus groups. Besides dedicated work groups within the plenary CoP meetings, each LL has also been organising dedicated focus groups to discuss the acceptance issues of specific solutions (e.g., climate-ready certificates in Lisbon, water reuse in agriculture in Flanders) with policymakers and the most directly involved stakeholders and end-users.

1.5 Key learnings for acceptance of water innovation

In this report so far, we have reviewed studies on the social acceptance of water innovation, also gaining some understanding from previous research on energy technologies. We have presented some of the key conceptual models that have been used to analyse acceptance among policymakers, end-users of technologies and citizens. At this point, we outline the key learnings that will inform future work on the key barriers and drivers for the adoption of B-WaterSmart solutions.

- **Risk perceptions** – Perception of the current or future risks of water scarcity in their region should play a significant role in motivating consumers to adhere to water innovative technologies, be it water reuse or smart devices for metering consumption. However, this association is not linear, as broader values perspectives and personal experiences might have counterproductive effects. Developing solutions to find alternative sources of water should be communicated as part of a broader strategy for reducing total consumption, as it may be perceived as running counter to local cultures of water conservation (especially in drought-prone areas). As much environmental awareness as there might be in a given city or region, there is generally a better acceptance of water reuse for non-potable ends that do not imply a close contact and possible risks of contamination ('yuck' factor). The implementation of water reuse strategies and technologies requires a careful and integrated approach to risk analysis and communication, with timely, transparent, and accessible information provided. There is not much consistency regarding the concerns of consumers over data privacy, implying that they should be highly variable depending on the issues that might arise on public and mediatic agendas. Studies reviewed indicate that this is not a major concern, but it is important for consumers to have access and control over the data being collected by water meters.
- **Attitudes** – Attitudes towards water technologies will be influenced by any additional and perceived costs. Smart devices are perceived as an opportunity to gain more control over consumption data, and therefore possibly reduce the water bills, but better accepted if their installation is free for consumers. Low-income households especially have to be considered for future redistributive policy (reduced tariffs, subsidies). Social and cultural factors play a significant role in acceptance of water innovation. Social norms and value-driven attitudes, including perceptions of approval from significant others (e.g., family and friends), as well as personal moral values,

influence pro-environmental behaviours and approval of new technologies. The perceived 'water culture' of the local community should be considered and adequately understood through in-depth discussions (e.g., focus groups and communities of practice), in complement with quantitative surveys.

- **Trust and Justice** – Trust has been cited recurrently has a key factor for acceptance of water innovation technologies, especially trust in public institutions and water utilities. This factor varies a lot between regions and countries and is directly related to governance issues that are analysed in detail in our report “Proposal for a new governance model” (D5.5.). In some cases, trust in institutions is a significant barrier in adherence to water reuse, in other cases is the technology itself that might raise doubts, particularly if they require detailed consumption data (smart meters). While literacy and information are positively associated with acceptance of water innovations, an active engagement of the end-user with the tools (smart meters) is an advantage. Accessibility and affordability are key for the adoption of any new home-based technologies. For households, the sense that information from meters is managed in a transparent way, but also that they can directly access and control the data provided, is key for nurturing trust in the process. Users that are already using smart meters for other purposes (electricity) are in general more likely to adopt additional devices. This is a good indication for the future deployment of integrated metering and/or efficiency certification (water and energy).

Above all, this review demonstrates how an effective implementation of water-smart innovations requires a better understanding of the socio-economic contexts in the ground, which considers the nature of the local economies (e.g., tourist regions and its housing dynamics) as well as the particular values, needs and concerns of end-users (e.g., age group, income, social norms, values perspectives, technology literacy). Grounded on a deeper understanding of socio-economic dynamics, an integrated policy design and tailored communication strategy are required to ensure a just and sustainable transition in the water sector.

2 Methodology

The objective of this preliminary version of the report is to collect exploratory data that will help inform the plan for the assessment of social acceptance issues in the final year of the project (Task 5.3) and for the final version of the report. The qualitative data collected from these key informant interviews will help construct the instruments for collecting data over the next few months (e.g., surveys to a sample of end-users). In some LLs, surveys are being carried out, but their results are not yet available for inclusion in this preliminary version of the report.

The methodology followed in D5.4 was two-fold and tailored to the context of each LL and its CoPs, at this point in the Project. As CoP roadmaps have different priorities for each meeting, considering the type of stakeholders involved and the solutions under discussion, we gathered inputs from both the meetings (and/or in-between focus groups held with CoP members at the LLs) and interviews with key stakeholders. These served to complement information on the key issues of acceptance, especially in those cases where the discussions taking place at the CoPs had not yet addressed the topic extensively. In cases where acceptance of solutions had been a key topic for the CoPs (such as Venice) we did not resort to these complementary interviews.

This methodology, as well as the contents of the report, were discussed and refined with the WP5 team members at the monthly meetings held from February to June 2023. The LL solutions (technologies and tools) considered for the purposes of this analysis of social acceptance were selected, according to criteria discussed between the LLs and the WP5 team. Only those that are most relevant and which implementation and replication will likely raise more issues were contemplated. This selection also benefited from previous work carried out to identify drivers and barriers for the implementation of the solutions, as well as socio-economic metrics for the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework (Task 5.2). The main documents for reference in this context are [D5.2. – Socioeconomic metrics for the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework](#) and [D5.3 – Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions Across 6 Cases: Policy and Governance](#).

Drawing from the MS7 analytical model, the MS18 report (August 2022, confidential to the consortium) compiled selected issues for this preliminary assessment:

- **risk perceptions** - Type of positions manifested during meetings regarding this solution – e.g., notions of water scarcity; possible risks to public health resulting from the solution (e.g., water reuse);
- **trust and Justice** - Type of positions manifested during meetings regarding (1) trust in management authorities and water utilities; (2) notions of fairness on e.g., information transparency, accessibility and affordability;
- **attitudes** - Level of acceptability and manifested intention to adopt the solution, for these target groups;
- Other relevant issues raised that might act as barriers (or also drivers) for the adoption of the solution by these target groups,

Multiple participatory methods were used during the CoP meetings since early 2021 following the guidelines provided by D1.1. (CoPs Architecture and Stakeholder Mapping) and D5.1. (Manual on Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement). According to the CoP Roadmaps established at the early stage of B-WaterSmart, we employed methods for assessing barriers and drivers, as well as discussing future options and scenarios (e.g., SWOT, PESTLE), resorting to collaborative digital tools (e.g., Groupmap, Mentimeter).

Besides the guidelines for direct observation and data collection (on risk perceptions, trust, notions of justice and attitudes towards the project solutions), the criteria for selecting interviewees and the guidelines for interviews have been discussed and prepared over several WP5 meetings. Table 1 is updated from MS18 and was provided to the WP5 team members (co-authors of this report) to be filled in with information collected from the CoP meetings for D5.4.

Table 1 – Key components of the social acceptance model

Solution / topic	Target group	Risk perceptions	Attitudes	Trust and Justice
		D5.4 (social acceptance & behaviours)	D5.4 (social acceptance & behaviours)	D5.4 & D5.5. (New governance models)
Please indicate the specific solution/digital tool in analysis (of those already covered at the meetings) or broader topic, if not applicable	Indicate if: (1) policymakers & regulators; (2) market agents; (3) households & citizens; (4) other stakeholders (which?) –	Please describe what type of positions were manifested during meetings regarding possible implications of the solution – e.g., risks to public health; economic risks; e.g., future affordability for users	Level of acceptability and manifested intention to adopt the solution, for this target group (opposition; neutral; intention to adopt)	Please describe what type of positions were manifested during meetings regarding – (1) trust in management authorities and water utilities (2) notions of fairness on e.g., information transparency, accessibility, and affordability

In addition to this, more detailed guidelines for the interviews were provided, with proposals for specific questions. These were discussed at the WP5 meetings and in bilateral meetings with the LL teams and were adjusted to the context of each solution and its respective stage of development. The interviewees were selected among stakeholders represented in the CoPs, both from government agencies and the industry, based on their level of responsibility and expertise. It is not possible to select the exact same type of key informants across the

LLs, for the purpose of this analysis, as these depend on a wide diversity of solutions under development in the project.

What socio-economic groups/sectors and actors (e.g., farmers, industry) are
- particularly supportive of this solution (and why)?
- particularly critical (and why)?

What concerns about such a solution do you expect from specific socio-economic groups and/or society at large?

What are the main drivers for greater acceptance of the solution? (e.g., *legal/political framework, societal trends, economic development*)

Will this solution have implications in terms of justice issues/notions – e.g., *distributive issues regarding the costs, increase in prices or tariffs, groups that might be more affected*

Which measures are suitable to ensure / increase the acceptance of this solution? (e.g., *legal, technical, financial, communication, organisational...*)

COVID-19: What influence might the societal experience of the Covid-19 pandemic have on the acceptance of such a solution? How to improve **resilience** in the sector, ensuring an effective and long-term implementation of the LL solutions?

Gender: Does this solution have gender-relevant aspects for you (which ones?) that need to be taken into account in the implementation (how?)? E.g., have women been adequately represented in the sector?

The following chapters present the analysis of the key issues of acceptance – at socio-political, market and community levels – identified for each Living Lab in B-WaterSmart. The chapters were elaborated by the WP5 team and validated by the LL owners and mentors (co-authors indicated for each chapter), according to the guidelines provided.

The insights collected from CoP participants and interviewees are under ongoing analysis and reflect their own views. The affirmations and opinions indicated in tables and text do not imply a consensus on the discussed matters among the LL members or CoP participants.

3 Key acceptance issues for B-WaterSmart LLs

3.1 Alicante

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Alicante, situated in southeastern Spain, is characterized by its semi-arid nature, leading to infrequent and limited rainfall, thereby posing a water supply challenge. With scarce local water resources available, the region adopts a multifaceted approach to water sourcing to ensure reliability. The water supply comprises 33% groundwater from inland areas, supplemented by surface water harnessed through the Tajo-Segura water transfer system, Taibilla River, and seawater desalination. Additionally, nearly half of treated wastewater is reclaimed to cater to urban, agricultural, and recreational needs.

Thus, water reuse emerges as a viable approach to ensure a stable water supply for the region and offers the possibility to go further in the water circularity, aimed at harnessing energy, nutrients, and chlorine from reclaimed water. In this sense, new technologies and methodologies are investigated in Alicante to boost water reuse, resource recovery and circular economy around the urban water cycle. These proposed solutions are:

- Energy recovery from sewage treatment plant effluents and organic waste through co-digestion.
- Recovery of nutrients from the sludge line to produce fertilizers.
- Production of disinfectants from brine from the regeneration of reclaimed water.

It is remarkable that the implementation of water smart solutions is not devoid of obstacles, as, for example, technical impediment arises from the heightened salinity content in certain wastewater streams, as well as barriers in garnering acceptance for water reuse practices.

In this report, the analysis will focus on the barriers to social acceptance of the solutions proposed by the Alicante LL, as **understanding stakeholder perceptions and attitudes towards the solutions is very important for a smooth implementation and uptake**.

The engagement of stakeholders is achieved mainly through the Communities of Practice (CoP) across the LLs. In LL Alicante, a total of 4 CoP meetings have been organised so far. The Communities of Practice is composed by a good number of participants from different backgrounds, such as water-related associations, start-ups, administration, water-users (as irrigators), NGOs, citizen representatives, academia, industry, and other local communities.

In the **first CoP** the community was officially set-up and all participants accepted and understood their role and were willing to give their feedback and participate in the discussions. Initially, three working groups (Urban, Agro-industry, Environmental) collaboratively envisioned water management in their sectors for 2050. Following this, the **main challenges and barriers** obstructing the achievement of this vision were identified, as well as the **potential strategies to overcome these challenges** in the future.

The **second CoP** was carried out online. The discussion revolved around the strategic agenda and encompassed several key steps, including **the prioritization of the Strategic**

Objectives and well-defined targets of the Long-Term Plan, identifying initiatives required to achieve each objective, and subsequently prioritizing these proposed initiatives to ensure effective resource allocation and implementation. The **third CoP** was focused on the **agricultural sector**. The objective was to **identify main challenges and barriers in the agriculture field related to water availability**, energy consumption, use of fertilizers and digital tools. Finally, the **fourth CoP** had the focus on **urban areas**. The event aimed at identifying the primary challenges and opportunities of the **implementation of reclaimed water and other resources** derived from WWTPs (as fertilizers) within the urban confines of Alicante.

The relevant findings from the CoP meetings regarding the stakeholders attitudes towards water-smart solutions are translated in table 2:

Table 2 - Observations on social acceptance from 1st and 2nd CoP meeting

Solution / topic	Target groups	Risk perceptions	Trust and Justice	Attitudes
<p>1st CoP: Solutions for the future of Cities: Environment, Agriculture, and Industry.</p> <p>2nd CoP: Discussion of the LL strategic agenda and prioritization of strategic objectives</p>	<p>1st CoP: NGOs, Local administration, Professional associations; Environmental experts, Regional Administration, Academics; Agriculture representatives, Industry associations.</p> <p>2nd CoP: Agriculture representatives, Authorities, Industry, Research, Utilities, NGOs, Associations</p>	Lack of public participation and awareness was found to be a relevant issue. Many sectors of society were not fully concerned with the value of water and a reliable water supply and management at low cost was always taken for granted.	To ensure a fair water management "water price should take into account its availability" and there should be (encouraging) legislation, economic incentives, and financial support, especially for small projects or initiatives.	General positive attitude and very high interest especially towards increasing the use of reclaimed water.
		Environmental experts highlighted the lack of knowledge of the costs of no-action and a need to quantify the environmental value of water.	There is a need for involving local development agencies.	Some scepticism among the representatives from agriculture and industry due to financial and legislative barriers.
		For the agriculture and industry sectors, lack of funding may be a barrier in addressing water scarcity.		

		Lack of transport/storage infrastructures, as well as a need to improve contingency plans for critical infrastructures		
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Table 3 - Observations on social acceptance from the 3rd CoP meeting

Solution / topic	Target groups	Risk perceptions	Trust and Justice	Attitudes
Challenges of the Agriculture in the future - Focus Group	End users - 3 representatives	Oversaturation of technologies and applications – they are not unified and do not allow interpreting data that is useful to farmers	Establish lines of action and agreed objectives between the different key actors (irrigation communities, farmers, administration, etc.)	Boost social awareness toward acceptance of products irrigated with reclaimed water
	Engineering companies - 2 representatives	There is stigma on products irrigated with reclaimed water	Environmental awareness - everyone's task and especially administration	Involve big distribution chains to analyse and track the consumer habits
	NGOs - 1 representative	Many bureaucratic barriers to applying for financial support for the implementation of solutions	Public-private collaboration including the end-user for innovation projects from their conception	Consulting/support/training in the use of digital technologies could actually be more important than the development of new tools
	Research institutes - 3 representatives	Reclaimed water also generates waste (brine) that needs to be managed	Provide scientific support (academia) to promote the certification of products irrigated with reclaimed water	The implementation of digital technologies depends on the size of the farms and their characteristics

Table 3 - Observations on social acceptance from 4th CoP meeting

Solution / topic	Target groups involved	Risk perceptions	Trust and Justice	Attitudes
Challenges of the Urban water cycle - Focus Group	Specialized media - 2 representatives	Attendees see possible uses of reclaimed water in some applications that are not yet regulated, so the perception of risks may not be problematic.	In relation to housing law, technical building regulations can play a crucial role in water conservation, both in residential buildings and in facilities like air conditioning, where wastewater can be reused for community activities.	The attendees proposed uses of reclaimed water that go beyond what is allowed in the legislation, so that its acceptance seems to be advanced.
	Academia - 1 representative			
	Sectorial entities - 3 representatives	Current legislation may present obstacles to more effectively implement water-saving measures, necessitating a revision of the existing laws.	The energy cost associated with water consumption, particularly in heating water, may be a more relevant incentive for the population than the monetary cost of water itself.	Promoting gamification and comparing consumption with neighbours can be effective strategies to encourage water conservation, utilizing behavioural sciences.
	Research institutes - 1 representative		Implementing incentives, such as providing additional water for every cubic meter saved, can encourage water conservation, and discourage excessive usage.	Lack of awareness regarding water reuse in Alicante is highlighted as a problem, indicating the need for improved communication, education in schools and public information.
	Local associations - 2 representatives			

To complement the information provided in the table above, additional information on social acceptance has been collected through interviews with local actors. The aim of conducting interviews was to assess the social acceptance of the smart solutions proposed in the project to collect qualitative information on the attitudes, beliefs and perceptions of the people involved in the project. These interviews provide an understanding of how the community perceives and accepts smart solutions and circular approaches to water management.

Concretely, three interviews were carried out with stakeholders to assess risk perceptions regarding water scarcity in Alicante, as well as the level of social acceptability of water-smart solutions in the region. We summarize here the main conclusions that offered contributions to our analysis on social acceptance of the B-Water Smart project solutions.

3.1.1 Risk perceptions

Although some awareness about water scarcity and the necessity of innovative solutions exists, the **general population often lacks action-taking**. Campaigns advocating responsible water consumption were prevalent a decade ago, but recent years have witnessed a dearth of clear messages, particularly among newer generations. This situation has led to **a risk perception gap and a growing belief that technology alone can solve water scarcity**, which fosters inactivity and a sense of complacency.

Furthermore, the **accessibility of information on innovative solutions remains inadequate**, with the general public lacking easily understandable details about water scarcity and potential remedies. The available information primarily targets those already interested in the topic, **limiting its reach to a broader population**. That is to say, concerns about water scarcity tend to be more focused on environmental contexts (relying heavily on specialised sources) and **the limited information from the general local press channels is a constraint**.

On the other hand, there appears to be **minimal opposition to innovative solutions**, even within environmentalist circles. However, **mistrust regarding the composition of reclaimed water and apprehensions about solid waste** pose hurdles to its acceptance, mainly due to a lack of information. In this sense, visual experiments and informative events should be organized to address these concerns and foster a culture of reuse among the society.

Finally, the **payment for these solutions seems to be a focus of risk perception** among interviewees. At the population level, **citizens should not bear additional costs for water smart solutions**. For its part, the industrial sector might consider an overcost of the innovative water services if they improve operations and get an added value service.

3.1.2 Notions of justice

The B-Water Smart solutions hold potential for **driving environmental and social justice** by rectifying unequal access to natural resources and promoting sustainability. The adoption of innovative water solutions can help strike a sustainable balance between human needs and ecosystem requirements, **preventing natural resource overexploitation, enhancing resource distribution, increasing water availability, encouraging citizen participation, and safeguarding resources** for future generations. Furthermore, it has the potential to **generate jobs, enhance food security and improve social welfare** in the long term.

With regard to the **additional costs of innovation** in the water cycle, this should **not be borne directly by the population**, but should be borne by large consumers and administrations to comply with social justice.

The government institutions and media currently fall short in **democratizing access to data**, as information largely remains confined to specialized channels rather than reaching the wider public. Measures to encourage justice encompass **street-level dissemination of information, educational campaigns, community center talks, engagement with influential community members, and active community participation in decision-making processes** related to reclaimed water.

In terms of **gender sensitivity**, women's meaningful involvement is emphasized to boost justice, as they are seen as effective communicators for recommending and supporting these solutions within family economies.

3.1.3 Attitudes towards water-smart solutions

Acceptance and rejection of water solutions exhibit **variations across sectors and groups**. With regards to the general population, children and the young population tend to be more open to innovative water solutions, influencing their closest adult relatives, while **older individuals may resist change due to deeply entrenched beliefs**. However, local associations and the general population appear receptive to reclaimed water for gardening. Thus, **active community engagement** is considered influential, involving committed individuals as advocates, and utilizing word-of-mouth strategies.

As regards the economic sectors, **scepticism persists in the agricultural sector** regarding the quality of reclaimed water, as it's perceived to have less quality compared to drinking water. On the other hand, **the industrial sector may show greater inclination towards acceptance**, owing to the absence of direct human contact in specific applications.

In this sense, **financial incentives could potentially foster greater receptivity** among sectors like agriculture and industry to circular and innovative water services, provided that the **general population doesn't bear additional costs**. Indeed, the willingness to pay for these solutions is low among the general population, primarily due to the prevailing economic situation, although industries with high water consumption might consider investing in their own water reuse systems.

Government institutions and media are recognized as vital in promoting reclaimed water, by creating educational videos and other resources through informal channels for a wider reach. Education, especially in schools, is seen as essential, emphasizing practical learning through experiments and pilots. Also municipalities are highlighted as key players, **concretely in promoting green areas and climate shelters** in urban areas.

In short, interviewees remarked that social acceptance requires **awareness campaigns and educational initiatives** to bridge the information gap and enhance public knowledge about water scarcity and innovative solutions. Suggestions also include **promoting urban greening and integrating innovative water solutions within schools**.

1.1.3 Synthesis of conclusions from CoP meetings & interviews

Alicante has a long history of optimizing water resources due to its climate, and this is made visible in the attitudes of the participants of the activities carried out within the LL. **Acceptance of water-smart solutions is pretty high** in all target groups involved so far and, in fact, the water reuse measures proposed by stakeholders go beyond what is required by law. But it is worth noting that, in the economic sectors of agriculture and industry there **is still some scepticism towards reclaimed water due to financial and legislative barriers**.

However, there is still a lot of **work to be done in terms of accessibility of information, training, and dissemination** so that the advances in the field of water reach all people,

especially vulnerable groups, which are the ones that have the greatest barriers to accessing information. Social justice and the protection of these groups must be ensured in the process of innovation in the water sector. Furthermore, **the extra cost of implementing innovative water solutions should not be borne directly by the population**, maintaining socially fair water tariffs.

Although there may still be people who are reluctant to reuse water, this barrier could be overcome through the **active involvement of local groups** to carry out demonstrations, experiments, and other educational activities in which they can take part. With a special focus on children and adolescents, who are great transmitters of information to their relatives and the catalyst for change in the long-term. Also, **government institutions and media play a key role in promoting reclaimed water**, by creating educational videos and other resources through informal channels for a wider reach.

Ultimately, there is a need to **emphasize the value of the environmental asset of water** and the **consequences of not taking action** in a rigorous manner by using studies and data. Moreover, enhancing the responsible use of water can be achieved by **introducing incentives or gamified services grounded in behavioral sciences**.

3.1.4 Other issues: COVID-19 and gender

While the pandemic has presented difficulties in the water sector, it has also brought some benefits. It has **strengthened team resilience, promoted better coordination, and facilitated more detailed planning**. Additionally, it has emphasized the importance of **wastewater-based epidemiology, improved digital monitoring of water, and identified weaknesses in emergency procedures** that require improvements.

Overall, no significant changes in user attitudes toward water-smart solutions have been observed due to the pandemic. However, new needs related to **water quality monitoring and health control in wastewater have been identified**.

Collaboration and cooperation among different actors, such as local administrations, have increased in promoting and adopting water-smart solutions during the pandemic, particularly in the wastewater-based epidemiology area.

In terms of user trust, it has generally remained stable, and **measures have been taken to ensure water safety**, such as continuous COVID-19 presence analysis, which has contributed to building confidence in the water sector.

Regarding regulatory frameworks, **recommendations and standardizations have been made to improve analysis procedures and laboratory methodologies** in response to the pandemic. Furthermore, the COVID pandemic has encouraged public financing (1M€) in the **digitalisation of the water sector** through the Next Generation programme.

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic has presented significant challenges in implementing water-smart solutions, but it has also **fostered improvements** in team resilience, coordination, and detailed project planning. Moreover, greater **knowledge of digital solutions and wastewater-based epidemiology has emerged**. This has led to a better collaboration and collective trust in the water sector.

The LL does **not have specific mechanisms to track gender equality** aspects, such as statistics, quotas, equality plans, or resource distribution. However, within the water sector, which is highly male-dominated due to its association with science, engineering, and technology, efforts are made to **promote gender balance in participatory actions**. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that **there is still room to increase the representation of women** (for example as speakers) in all possible activities of the project to provide them with greater visibility in the sector.

Regarding the results of the project, **both men and women are expected to benefit similarly from the project's results**, however, no specific analysis has been conducted to assess this aspect. Although generally speaking females care more about environmental issues and engage in more conservation behaviours than males, in participatory activities (workshops, interviews, etc.), **no major gender difference has been perceived so far**.

Overall, the analysis highlights the need for increased gender diversity and inclusion within the LL group (both the team and stakeholders) and emphasizes the importance of considering gender perspectives in various aspects, including representation and analysis of attitudes, among others. **There is a great opportunity to make further contributions to promoting gender equality and visibility within the project before its completion.**

3.2 Bodø

Co-authors: Sigrid Damman; Henrik Brynthe Lund (SINTEF)

The solutions discussed in the case of the Bodø LL in B-WaterSmart are smart water meters and nature-based solutions (NBS) for stormwater management. In the following sections, we will discuss social acceptance issues for the two, based on observations in CoPs. There has not been CoP meetings covering the topic of smart water meters. A CoP meeting on surface water management was held in March 2022. Additional information concerning NBS has been collected through two interviews with property developers identified as important by partners in Bodø municipality.

3.2.1 Risk perceptions

Sense of urgency

Bodø is currently not facing any challenges concerning water scarcity. The fact that this region has had an abundance of water resources reflects on the **low collective awareness** on the part of the population, who has never experienced serious shortages. The current situation, where the inhabitants pay for water based on the size of their homes, as there are very few water meters installed within the municipality, further demonstrates this.

Although water scarcity is not an issue in Bodø but improving public awareness in relation to climate change impacts on water, stormwater management, etc. is on the agenda. However, there does not seem to be a sense of urgency concerning stormwater and how **NBS** could be part of the solution for handling stormwater.

Trust

On a general level, the level of trust towards Bodø municipality and the water utilities seems to be high. This is in line with a broader study on trust in water governance in Northern Norway, which describes the level of trust as high, and relates it to the history of high trust in political authorities in Norway in general.¹ The issue of trust is particularly relevant in relation to the implementation of smart-water meters, where issues concerning GDPR has been a key challenge for the municipality when installing the smart-meters. The handling of data and sharing of data with a third-party (the technology providers) has been the main challenge. It is essential that Bodø handles this properly in the ongoing initial demonstration phase, to promote trust between the municipality and its inhabitants, which could help foster widespread implementation of the technology later on.

3.2.2 Notions of justice

The covering of additional costs for implementing of smart water-meters and NBS is one point of contention in the Bodø LL. The interviews with real-estate developers demonstrated that

¹ <https://vannforeningen.no/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Fedreheim.pdf>

there is uncertainty concerning who is to cover the cost of NBS. Currently, one real-estate developer is positive towards more emphasis on and demands for NBS in the development of new property areas, yet is unsure of how the municipality will follow up on this and how the extra costs concerning NSB will be covered. Concerning the smart water-meters, it is not clear how the cost of these will be covered if the solution is scaled within the municipality. It is however likely that they will be similar to the water meter scheme that exists in Bodø today, where the households rent the water meter from the municipality². However, more accurate measure of water consumption could lead to lower water fees for households that use less water than what is the norm (based on size in m³) today.

There are no prevalent social justice issues concerning the implementation of **smart-water meters**. However, previous studies have shown that tenants living in rented homes might worry that it could affect their water bill in a negative way, meaning increasing costs of living. There is currently a debate in Norway on municipalities right or not to require **nature-based solutions** on private land, and the question who should then pay, the developer or the municipality. Some of the statements in CoP workshop suggest that it is easier for larger developers to find ways around requirements and requests in this area, than for smaller developers. As such, there could be potential challenges related to justice between small and large developers, if the small ones are burdened by additional costs for NBS.

3.2.3 Attitudes

Concerning NBS, one of the interviewed property developers expressed that implementing NBS in urban environments is a challenge as buildings need to handle the additional weight of draining masses and vegetation. An additional challenge is how to handle ice and snow, and the increased maintenance costs of maintaining the NBS. Bodø recently introduced the Blue-green factor, which entails development of NBS that can handle stormwater challenges. The blue-green factor should promote NBS and is something that should be factored in when the municipality reviews new construction applications.

Concerning attitudes towards water consumption recent surveys have shown that less than half of all Norwegians regards efforts to reduce water consumption as an important environmental measure³. Furthermore, less than 17% believe that measures to reduce water consumption at home are among the most important environmental measures. Building on this, the level of water meter coverage in Norway is low. As an example, only 1,5% of households in Oslo, the capital city, had installed water meters in 2015⁴.

Awareness

Public awareness concerning **smart-water meters** seems to be low. This could be related to the fact that regular smart meters are not widespread in Bodø households, thus the public does not have a clear perception on the use of water meters in general, and consequently

² <https://bodo.kommune.no/vei-vann-og-avlop/vann-og-avlop/tilknytningsgebyr-arsgebyr-og-vannmaler/vannmaler/>

³ <https://www.nemitek.no/oras-vannsparing/nordmenn-bryr-seg-minst-om-vannsparing-i-norden/116601>

⁴ https://vannforeningen.no/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/2015_929348.pdf

limited awareness concerning smart water meters. For NBS, public awareness seems limited. Following interviews with property developers, it seems as though the awareness is varied. Whereas one developer had much knowledge on the benefits of NBS, how they can contribute to better quality living and provide increased value for property developers if done right, another had limited knowledge and was rather unfamiliar with NBS and seemed unsure of what position the municipality is going take on implementation of NBS, and how this will be treated in building applications.

3.3. East Frisia

Co-authors: **David Schwesig; Andreas Hein (IWW); Julia Oberdörffer (OOWV)**

3.3.1. Context, scope, and methodology of assessing social acceptance

The main challenges and objectives of the LL East Frisia are comprehensively described in e.g., deliverable D1.7 (section 6.4), in milestone document MS06 (first long-term vision, section 3.3), and in MS22 (strategic agenda agreed by CoP, section 3.3), and hence will not be repeated here in detail. In a nutshell, the solutions developed for LL East Frisia aim to identify untapped water resources, increase efficiency in water use and allocation, and to increase reuse of process water (as substitute for drinking water) in water-demanding key industries of the area such as the dairy industry.

Scope of the analysis

In the LL East Frisia, a detailed analysis of potential acceptance issues was carried out for the following two technologies that are developed and demonstrated in this Living Lab:

- #6: Treatment of vapor condensate / milk & whey permeate for re-use in dairy industry.
- #28 Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (STDFT), based on the use of smart meter data.

For these two technologies, preliminary discussions in the CoPs and with various stakeholder groups had indicated that acceptance and official approval of these solutions can be an issue for their application and implementation. The other two technologies developed and demonstrated within LL East Frisia (#23 Regional demand-supply GIS tool and #22 Extended UWOT model) are mainly tools for internal use of the LL owner OOWV. Hence, social acceptance issues for these latter solutions are not relevant and are not being analysed within B-WaterSmart.

Methodology

A targeted discussion on the dimensions of the B-WaterSmart acceptance model for technologies #6 and #28 did not fit the scope and schedule of the CoP-Meetings carried out so far. Hence, specific qualitative interviews with selected individual CoP participants were conducted to understand barriers, drivers and relevant attitudes related to the acceptance of both solutions. For the two solutions, different interview partners were selected, based on a pre-identification of stakeholders and actors relevant for the specific technology in question. The interviews were structured along ten questions suitable to cover on the one hand the elements of the B-WaterSmart acceptance model and on the other hand to be sufficiently open and non-constricting to enable the interview partners bringing in aspects and attitudes that were unforeseen by the project team. The interviews were recorded and a paraphrasing summary of the statements of the interview partners was shared with the interview partners for their approval and clearance. To enable an unreserved atmosphere in the interviews, it was agreed with the interviewees that their identity will not be disclosed in this deliverable nor the publicly available supplementary material, only the category of stakeholder they (or their organization) represent are described.

3.3.2. Acceptance of the Short-Term Demand Forecast Tool

The tool is used to create water demand forecasts for the next 24 hours. The user (i.e., the water supplier) can interact with the graphical user interface to train machine learning models and use them to create and visualize demand forecasts for specific supply areas. It also

allows the user to aggregate forecasts for multiple smart meters to achieve the desired spatial resolution. If successfully implemented, the solution will enable predictive operation of processing and storage units in the water supply system, as well as a more effective management of the water infrastructure.

The interview was carried out as a group interview with three interviewees immediately after a CoP-Meeting on 15 May 2023. All interview partners are active members of the CoP, hence familiar with objectives of the tool and its relation to the challenges, objectives, and ambitions of the LL East Frisia, and aware of the public / consumer notions about technology & management solution of this nature. In particular, the interview partners were:

- a representative of a district office for the environment and civil engineering.
- a university researcher in the field of transformation research.
- a regional manager of a water supplier.

There was consensus among the interviewees that significant barriers regarding social acceptance of this solution are mainly on the part of the citizen, i.e., the customer of the water supplier. In detail, the drivers, and barriers towards social acceptance of this solution are described as follows.

3.3.2.1. Risk perceptions

Economic risk

There is an awareness in the public that data collection such as through smart meters is done with the aim of a change (e.g., towards “smart water tariffs”) in which there will always be winners and losers. Hence, there is a perceived risk of economic / financial disadvantages for the consumer through a new price structure or cost model.

Privacy and “transparent consumer” risk

The higher the resolution in data collection all the way to individual consumers, the higher the concerns and possible barriers on the part of consumers. For example, an individual consumer who fills a private pool several times a year and fears targeted queries or feels pressure to justify him-/herself when this consumption pattern is recorded. Consumers are averse to being transparent and put into a situation where they need to justify their consumption patterns and habits.

Possible countermeasures

Regarding the economic risk, the objective of the data collection and the current and future use needs to be communicated in a transparent way, also outlining possible economic benefits of the user through the realization of saving potentials. Higher clustering and aggregation in data collection is an effective countermeasure to deal with the “transparent consumer” risk but reduces the informative value and increases the risk of misinterpretation. A good balance is required to ensure acceptability and useability of the data. In the case of household-specific data collection, GDPR-compliant consent from the consumer and application-specific consent is a minimum requirement.

3.3.2.2. Trust, Justice, and other societal norms

Trust

The critical point is public trust in the actors who act and are primarily responsible. A current challenge, however, also perceived in the LL area, is the decreasing trust in state actors and "official" institutions. An attitude that is more characterized by assumptions and insinuations

is noticeable (e.g., insinuation that critical data and information are withheld or selected, or that unfair agreements exist among the actors). Trust cannot be secured solely by increasing the number of figures, data and facts provided: larger amounts of unexplained data are more likely to carry the risk that they will not be correctly interpreted but misinterpreted. It is important to create trust through transparency in the background and objectives of the measures, explaining: What societal problem do we have? What do we want or need to achieve? Where do we want to go and why? What are we doing in concrete terms?

Justice

In order not to conflict with justice notions, it needs to be clearly communicated that there is a balance and a trade-off for three sides: an advantage for the water supplier by better management of its resources and system, and increased security of supply for all, and an advantage for the individual consumer through the possibility of savings e.g., by learning and better controlling consumption patterns, using favourable consumption times, staying below threshold values to obtain cheaper tariffs.

The justice dimension can also be used as an argument in favour of the application of this solution: A single consumer can only be held responsible for its own consumption and is not aggregated in (and judged by) the consumption pattern of a whole district. On the contrary, the consumer has its own control options.

Fairness and equality

Any commitment and activity on the part of the customer in the form of conscious action must be adequately awarded but must also not be torpedoed by tolerating obviously counteracting measures and actions of other actors (e.g., large-scale use of agricultural irrigation systems or when industrial companies cool hall roofs with drinking water). This quickly leads to frustration and resignation ("What can I do on my own if larger players leave a much larger footprint without sanctions?"). The sense of justice and the sense of meaningfulness and effectiveness of individual action must be strengthened. It is not only about the fair distribution of costs, but also about the fair distribution of responsibility and opportunities for participation. Transparency and participation are fundamentally important. However, this does not mean that all individual opinions can be considered and implemented.

Sustainability

Sustainability is an increasingly accepted norm in the society. In the area of the LL East Frisia, there are environmentally conscious groups in the population, some of whom even admonish that water is too cheap at the moment and therefore the careful use of water as a resource not sufficiently promoted.

3.3.2.3. Other drivers, barriers and initiatives

Legal and political framework

A recently issued German National Water strategy as well as ongoing discussions at the level of political / professional industry associations (e.g., VKU – German Association of Local Public Utilities) supports solutions promoting more water-use efficiency and better management of water infrastructure.

Social perception

Awareness of water as an increasingly scarce commodity is increasing among the population. There are also voices that the price of water is still too low and does not sufficiently promote the economical use of the resource. Development towards a more sustainability-oriented attitude is growing and can support the acceptance of the solution. There is a significant

number of citizens who are aware of environmental and climate policy, sustainability-oriented, and well-informed. They are to be regarded as a rather open-minded group for smart metering and flexible prices.

On the other hand, groups of people with a particular sensitivity to data protection are more likely to be critical here. Data collection has a rather negative connotation among the German population. A rather negative attitude is expected from generally rather critical groups of people, climate change deniers and people with little attachment to social solidarity principles. Critical attitude also from sectors particularly affected by conflicts of use and competition for water resources e.g., agriculture and other water-intensive industries, where water consumption and price are a significant cost and location factor. The change away from staggered water tariffs ("volume discount"), which was only completed a few years ago, has now been accepted, but it will not be so easy to convey a flexibilization of prices even into the opposite direction.

There are also some reservations within the water supply companies, among employees who, for historical reasons, act from a primarily growth-oriented attitude (growth = sale of higher amounts of water).

Economic situation

The current economic development and high awareness of cost can support: The solution offers better possibility of cost control and cost reduction for the consumer. This should be accompanied by a political message that the water sector should remain in the public sector as a sovereign task, which would be helpful as a confidence-building measure.

Analogies to other sectors

Analogy to the energy sector: In the industry, the mainly mandatory introduction of an energy management system for companies was an important and now well-established measure. A corresponding system for water management in the industrial sector would be conceivable and sensible, which would bring us significantly forward on the way to a smarter water-smart society, on the one hand by raising awareness of water consumption, required quantities and qualities, but also by providing a better planning basis for utilities as well.

Municipal funding programmes

Municipal programmes or the development and use of alternative water sources for non-drinking water use (e.g., rainwater harvesting systems, infiltration systems) but also to relieve the infrastructure during heavy rainfall events (e.g., green roofs and facades) are well known and in high demand among parts of the population.

Gender dimension of the solution:

Not relevant.

3.3.2.4. Preliminary learnings guiding further work

For the implementation of the solution and future focal areas of the analysis of social acceptance, the following lessons can be drawn from this interview regarding suitable measures to secure or increase the acceptance of this solution:

- It is crucial to present the concrete and direct added value of the solution to the end customer. In the case of a smart meter, this could be, for example, an additional app that visualizes the information and points towards potential cost savings. Reasons and objectives for the action must be made transparent and the benefits not only for others (such as for the operator) but also specifically for the customer / end user. Explain to the consumer in an understandable way why and what for such a solution

is being sought. The objective must be made plausibly understandable to the public, including the advantages in financial terms (for all parties) and the relevance of safeguarding an essential service such as water supply for the whole society.

- Justice and fairness must clearly and credibly be explained as an important goal for the implementation.
- High-resolution data collection at household level is successfully done and accepted in other sectors (e.g., energy, telecommunications). This can be used as an argument and serve as a model for acceptance regarding the application of such approaches also in water supply. Also, for the industry, analogies with other sectors (e.g., mandatory energy management systems) can be exploited as supportive arguments.
- Transparent communication about the background, scope, and objectives of data collection is key to acceptance, in particular if the benefits to the end user are explained, ensuring that there is a just and fair distribution of the efforts, costs and benefits associated with the new solution.
- Compliance with high data security and privacy standards and all legal requirements including GDPR-compliant consent in case of household-specific data collection are a basic requirement.
- Risk perception can also work in favour of the acceptance of the solution. Awareness of the possible scarcity of water resources is increasing among the population. The use of such tools can support sensible management and the perceived self-efficacy / sovereignty of the consumer.
- The advantage of the water topic in this regard is that there is a growing perception of the need to manage the resources more sustainably, and the direct visibility and perceptibility of the measures on site.

3.3.3. Acceptance of the re-use of process water in the dairy industry

The objective of solution #6 is to enable the re-use of process water as a substitute for drinking water in direct contact with the (food) product. As the main barrier for this solution is the approval by the relevant authorities, two interviews were carried out with:

- a representative of a federal state authority for consumer protection and food safety
- a representative of a federal state authority for public health.

3.3.3.1. Main barriers to the acceptance of the solution

Legal

Compliance with the Drinking Water Ordinance (also in its forthcoming amended form), in connection with EU Regulation 852/2004.

The use of process water in dairies for pre-cleaning processes is not fundamentally new but has been established for some time. However, the planned use as final step of cleansing and disinfection in the final stage before the actual production process (in contact with food-containing tubes and/or the product) is new. Up to now, only drinking water has been explicitly permitted here.

Technical

The origin of the water used must be clearly traceable and monitorable. The use of treated water derived from food (e.g., from vapor condensate / permeate from whey) may possibly be permissible, but the use of treated water from the wastewater stream (pre-rinse or production outlet water) is not. Transparency in the execution and documentation of the technical processes and water flows is required, and proper inspection, surveillance and monitoring must be possible.

Hygiene

A higher hygienic risk is at least possible. Such concerns can only be overcome by solid facts. Hygienic risks certainly play a role as a barrier in public perception.

Sustainability concerns

Due to the high technical effort required to produce water of drinking quality from process water, environmental concerns can also be a barrier, because this solution may be seen as only shifting the problem: high energy costs for treatment and negative environmental effect if the energy used is not climate neutral. The need for stricter monitoring due to the specific origin of the raw water may also be associated with higher costs and become an additional barrier.

Public habits and attitudes

Another barrier are public habits. Drinking water is a sensitive issue and it is assumed by the population that it is predominantly obtained from protected resources such as (deep) groundwater. It is a new idea and sort of a paradigm shift that drinking water should be replaced by treated process water at some points, even in food production. Even if in other regions of Germany, for example, river water is treated to produce drinking water, the perception is still somewhat different here, because people tend to associate process water with a waste product. If this is to be consumed via the food chain, there's a different psychological barrier to be overcome than in the case of recycling/reuse of waste or by-products into other consumer products.

3.3.3.2. Main drivers for acceptance

Economic and environmental resource-efficiency

The most convincing advantage and hence a driver for acceptance is the saving of drinking water resources and the associated costs. In addition to the cost saving potential, a greater self-sufficiency and independence from externally procured drinking water are also supporting factors for the uptake of this solution. The sustainability dimension is a clear benefit of approaches to reuse process water. However, it only becomes convincing and sound as a truly resource-saving approach if the energy used for treatment is also generated in a climate neutral way.

Technical feasibility

The building blocks of the technology required for use of vapour condensate from whey (e.g., for pre-cleansing) is state of the art, hence the ambition is understandable to further extend the application.

Sustainability and water scarcity present in media and politics

Greater media presence of the issue of water scarcity, the need for water reuse, and the reflection of these issues e.g., in new European directives on water reuse are supportive for the acceptance of this solution. The political environmental and climate goals also send a signal to the population, especially because these are no longer niche topics but are taken seriously across party lines and are included in the form of political and social goals in broadly supported programs. The social trend towards an increased sustainability is also omnipresent in the public discussion, a clear sensitization of the population for environmentally oriented action has taken place in recent years, also reinforced by the experience of the Covid-19 pandemic. Political initiatives at state and federal level on climate protection and sustainable management of water resources, as well as the experience of water shortage situations (irrigation bans in dry periods) also support the acceptance of such solutions. There is now a higher awareness of risks and possible crisis in the population than e.g., a decade ago.

3.3.3.3. Stakeholder with specific attitudes

Particularly supportive stakeholders

Environmentally educated citizens:

Citizens with a strong environmental awareness and sensitivity to sustainability approaches are generally open to such a solution. Environmental benefits and cost-saving potential are easy to see and to communicate. People with a high affinity to technology and a high level of environmental awareness will have a more positive attitude towards this solution. These are more represented in the younger generation (higher climate and environmental awareness than in the average population).

Technologically educated citizens or professionals

Here the interviewees offered different perspectives:

- One interview partner stated that people with a professional technology background, who can evaluate the performance of technical solutions for water treatment based on their specific knowledge, are expected to have a more open attitude.
- The second interview partner pointed out that people with more detailed technical-scientific knowledge of the relevant processes as well as knowledge of possible legal and hygienic risks are likely to be more critical (although they can be convinced by facts). This is especially true for individuals who also bear responsibility for the factual

and legal consequences of a licensing decision. The greater the responsibility, the stronger the critical attitude.

Other specific groups

Support can be expected by those who have directly experienced water scarcity or water shortage situations and public calls to save water (e.g., garden watering bans), or who work in particularly water-intensive sectors where conflicts of use are also present (e.g., agriculture). Environmental protection organisations are also expected to be supportive to this sort of technology.

Particularly critical stakeholders

Technology-critical and general sceptics

Rather technology-critical persons or people with fundamental scepticism and general concerns about the quality of drinking water. People with little contact to (and knowledge of) technology; rather ideologically motivated consumer protection organisations.

As pointed out above, health authorities / consumer protection authorities are expected to be rather cautious or even sceptical for technical reasons but can be convinced with solid factual arguments.

Broader public

Usually, concerned citizens first approach the competent communal / municipal authority for food surveillance. There is an anonymous reporting centre at the state level that citizens can contact if they have concerns about food hygiene. However, most reports relate to other aspects (e.g., animal protection or violation of food law). There is also an EU-wide rapid alert system for concerns or infringements related to food laws, and complaints from third countries are also recorded. So, there are several mechanisms to register concerns of the public. However, the technology in question here does not currently play a role there.

3.3.3.4. Other barriers and drivers

Societal norms

Equal treatment

In particular relevant for authorities in the approval process: there must be no unlawful favourable administrative act, and the principle of equal treatment must not be violated. *The latter must be upheld not only within a federal state, but also nationally and within the EU.*

Justice

Intergenerational justice plays a role here through the idea of sustainability: this solution contributes to the protection and more sustainable management of the water resources, and thus ensures intergenerational justice (ensuring that current use of resources does not compromise irrevocably the access of future generations to resources to meet their own needs, in line with Brundtland's concept of sustainable development).

Trust & transparency

Trust in the relevant actors and organisations will be crucial for acceptance. The sector from which the pioneer companies for such solutions come will also play a role here. The dairy industry surely has a more positive image than e.g., slaughterhouses. This is a bonus. Transparency of the approval processes and involvement of all relevant authorities and stakeholders is important. Hence, it is important to establish the legal basis and technical rules for a sound legal and technical evaluation this solution. Establish appropriate

parameters and monitoring strategies. Transparency about the requirements and their compliance.

Reasonable timeline of decision-making

A critical point is the speed of decision-making. The citizen expects speedy decisions. In Germany, decision-making processes as defined by the assignment of competences and responsibilities sometimes take longer than would be desirable.

Enabling factors in the industry

The technical processes must be able to be monitored and secured. Here, the companies must also make organisational changes, e.g., in the adaptation of HACCP concepts and the development of emergency concepts, which guarantee hygienically safe production even in the event of technical failures / malfunctions.

Gender dimension

Not relevant for this solution.

Influence of the societal experience of covid-19 pandemics

The pandemic has given the starting signal for a higher crisis sensitivity among the population. Resources previously taken for granted, such as water, electricity, gas, are no longer taken for granted. There is a greater understanding that it makes sense to also look ahead for ways to save and find substitute solutions for these resources. This can be a supporting factor for acceptance of this solution.

3.3.3.5. Preliminary learnings guiding further work

For the implementation of the solution and future focal areas of the analysis of social acceptance, the following lessons can be drawn from the interviews with regard to suitable measures to secure or increase the acceptance of this solution. They will be taken into account for the further activities of the LL Frisia within WP1 (CoP), WP2 (technology demonstration) and WP5 (Society, governance, policy):

- Work towards clarity regarding the legal and technical requirements for this solution
- Provide suitable data proving with greatest possible clarity and transparency how the process fulfils the legal and technical requirements and does not lead to increased hygienic risks.
- Organise exchange and discussion between the stakeholders involved in the approval process (in particular municipal authorities, state authorities, state ministries).
- Organise a more intense direct exchange across authorities of different federal states, in particular among authorities in whose area of responsibility similar technologies are or will be operated.
- Raise awareness with the industry partners that adequate organizational changes need to be implemented (e.g., adjustment of HACCP concepts, development of emergency concepts) to enable proper monitoring and securing of the processes and a hygienically safe production under any circumstances.
- In communication make use of a) the supportive societal trend towards economically and environmentally sustainable solutions b) the positive image of the dairy industry as 'early adopter' of this solution c) clear and easy messages how this supports important societal and political strategies; d) helps to avoid scarcity and conflict-of-use situations.

3.4. LL Flanders

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3.4.1. Key issues of social acceptance

Flanders faces water challenges due to a combination of high drinking water demand due to the dense population, high irrigation water demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, and water scarcity due to droughts and climate change. Transforming the regional water system from linear to fully circular, by integrating the urban and natural water cycles, is critical for securing a freshwater supply for all sectors. Especially after the droughts of the last several years (e.g. 2017-2020), there is strong interest to explore alternative water sources and work towards a more robust, water-smart system.

Climate change is expected to lead to increased drought periods but also to more frequent extreme rainfall events. The LL Flanders strategic agenda specifically looks towards mitigation of the impact on drinking water production, stormwater management and water as a resource for agriculture. This is achieved by reusing water, maximising alternative water resources, and improving water use efficiency.

As such, the activities in LL Flanders help to assess the regional water system and its potential for water-smart solutions. These include closing water cycles, increasing resilience and integrating the existing natural water system as a nature-based solution while ensuring safe reuse close water cycles. At a local scale, technical demonstrations are developed based on alternative sources and effluent reuse for drinking water, and storm water management and reuse for agriculture. The experiences from these demonstration sites are used to identify the potential for the valorisation of the applied technologies at a larger scale at those locations, as well as at other locations. In this regard, understanding stakeholder perceptions and attitudes towards the solution is important.

The engagement of stakeholders is achieved through the communities of practice, across the LLs. In LL Flanders, a total of 3 CoP meetings have been organised by the time of D5.4. The first and second CoP meetings focused on sharing practical lessons (knowledge, technology, infrastructure, and business models) to accelerate and scale up circular and smart water use and to test the concept strategic agenda within the framework of B-WaterSmart. In consultation with the CoP stakeholders, the third CoP meeting addressed the decoupling of the human water chain (householders) and the water systems, looking at the steps that should be taken, and reuse of WWTP effluent.

Within LL Flanders, the CoP meetings roadmap was organised into different stages, in such a way to prompt discussion beyond the topic of costs and value of water (financing and business model). In fact, CoP members have been encouraged to discuss aspects of the technology and infrastructure itself, knowledge and skills needed, as well as the institutional regulations in place or needed for a smart-water management/water-smart technologies, for both effluent reuse and stormwater reuse. The backcasting technique was used to create a common vision for a water-smart Flanders in the horizon of 2050 (online CoP #1), looking at both the current situation and what is needed to achieve a water-smart society in the coming years. Then the CoP stakeholders started by selecting one scenario (decoupling human

water cycle from the natural water system) and identified possible steps to achieve it (CoP#2 in Blankaart). Part of such discussions is about the financial sustainability of different options, so this aspect is always in the back of stakeholders' minds, however financial sustainability needs to be discussed in a structured way. In the most recent CoP (CoP#3 in Mechelen), a more structured conversation was facilitated to understand what is needed to build a sustainable future for the case in Mechelen (stormwater reuse) and explore innovative business and governance models for stormwater management.

The relevant findings from the CoP meetings are translated in the table below according to the two different solutions/topics that are being researched in LL Flanders within B-WaterSmart. The Focus is not only on the solutions, but the outcomes are also applied to a broader scope.

Table 4 - Observations on social acceptance from CoP meetings

Solution / topic	Target group	Risk perceptions	Attitudes	Trust and Justice
Potential effluent reuse for drinking water (#3)	<p>Policymakers and regulators; Households & citizens; Research institutes</p>	<p>The work required to obtain a permit is quite extensive, even for small pilots and demonstration of technologies at a very small scale.</p> <p>Not everyone (on different levels e.g., households) is willing to take responsibility regarding water supply (drinking water, rainwater use...).</p> <p>The right quality for the right application is required.</p> <p>Regulations are based on price; it would be better to base them on risk.</p>	<p>Low awareness about water treatment costs may act as a barrier to the implementation of treatment solutions.</p> <p>Initiatives with citizen participation are difficult to set-up, due to lack of interest.</p> <p>Based on a survey from 2022, findings show varying degree of acceptability depending on the type of water. Research has been</p>	<p>Liberalisation of the water market is necessary to become less dependent on the major players⁵</p> <p>Effluent reuse should only be for local stakeholders.</p> <p>We should move away from a first come first serve principle, a masterplan is needed. Plan for prioritization is needed.</p> <p>Role of funding: should infrastructure projects always be funded, if they the business model is</p>

⁵ In Flanders, the minister is taking actions to narrow down the number of drinking water companies. The minister believes there are too many drinking water companies for the number of inhabitants. This remark reflects the opinion of one of the attendees of the CoP meeting and does not imply a consensus on this matter among LL or CoP members.

Solution / topic	Target group	Risk perceptions	Attitudes	Trust and Justice
		<p>Impact on ecosystem services.</p> <p>Need for a clear research and innovation agenda.</p> <p>There is a lot of confidence towards drinking water companies to delivery drinking water with a good quality even when using effluent as source.</p>	<p>carried out, however, showing that the behaviour of stakeholders changes when a solution is implemented.</p> <p>Nevertheless, the philosophy of large consumers should be that investments in greater water availability will in the long run yield more than losses incurred in a crisis situation if no investments are made. Initiatives with citizen participation are difficult to set-up, due to lack of interest.</p> <p>Applications with continuous demand are likely to have a better business case.</p>	<p>already solid? Shouldn't we reserve the funding for umbrella organisations, knowledge institutes, safeguarding social importance, innovation...</p> <p>Combination of applications in effluent reuse should be considered.</p> <p>Cooperation in cooperatives with citizens seems to be a good idea. In such a way citizens are engaged and reap the benefits (co-creation).</p>
Stormwater reuse for agriculture (#5)	Policymakers and regulators; Farmers; Farmers associations/organisations; Research institutes	While stormwater is not considered 'reclaimed water', there will be a need to better define how it should be managed at regional level. A treatment before infiltration may be necessary. It is still to be determined who should	Based on a survey from 2022 shows varying degree of acceptability depending on the type of water. Research has been carried out,	Mechelen pilot: Building trust with the local farmers as well as citizens who live close to the site where the stormwater basis will be built is very important; Water infiltration will take

Solution / topic	Target group	Risk perceptions	Attitudes	Trust and Justice
		<p>carry the cost for such improved solutions.</p> <p>Impact on ecosystem services.</p> <p>Severe regulations are a barrier for infiltration (deep infiltration-ASR and shallow infiltration-MAR)</p> <p>Need for a clear research and innovation agenda.</p> <p>Reuse of effluent should a replace a less sustainable source and may not cause extra water use.</p> <p>Due to the contact with water when using effluent for the irrigation of sport pitches, a thorough risk assessment must be carried out.</p>	<p>however, showing that the behaviour of stakeholders changes when a solution is implemented.</p> <p>Nevertheless, the philosophy of large consumers should be that investments in greater water availability will in the long run yield more than losses incurred in a crisis situation if no investments are made. Initiatives with citizen participation are difficult to set-up, due to lack of interest.</p> <p>Effluent reuse for agriculture is seen as difficult regarding quality.</p>	<p>place on their fields, therefore underpinned information about benefits and/or risks is needed to gain trust.</p> <p>With regards to water availability, there is a need for international agreements on water flow across borders, particularly for the Southwest region, where inflow of surface water is important.</p> <p>Effluent reuse should only be for local stakeholders.</p> <p>We should move away from a first come first serve principle, a masterplan and prioritisation are needed.</p> <p>Should infrastructure projects always be funded, if their business model is already solid? Shouldn't we reserve the funding for umbrella organisations, knowledge institutes, safeguarding social importance, innovation...</p>

Solution / topic	Target group	Risk perceptions	Attitudes	Trust and Justice
				<p>Combination of applications in effluent reuse should be considered.</p> <p>Cooperation in cooperatives seems a good idea, for citizens to engage and reap the benefits (co-creation).</p>

3.4.2. Insights from stakeholder interviews

To complement the information provided in the table above, additional information on social acceptance has been collected through interviews with Pidpa on potential effluent reuse for drinking water, and with the City of Mechelen and Inagro on stormwater reuse for agriculture. In addition to the interviews, several resources referenced in the interviews have also been used were relevant.

3.4.2.1. Potential effluent reuse for drinking water

The following sections will provide a synthesis of the findings from the interviews. This section will be partially structured using the conceptual model for social acceptance assessment used in B-WaterSmart.

Risk perceptions and attitudes

Decision makers, policymakers and regulators have generally accepted the reuse of effluent for agriculture and sports field irrigation, although there are some restrictions in place. Despite this, there are some sectors that are hesitant on the reuse of effluent for drinking water due to public perception, for example the breweries and malt factories. The intense contact between water and the product, such as grains in the malt production process, might raise concerns about taste and quality. Breweries also avoid using reused water in processes where there could be potential contact with their product. The public perception of using effluent in food and beverage production is a potential barrier/concern.

Industries (like the breweries and food processing industries) reusing effluent actively share about their use in the media. They use the platform to clarify that water used in the direct production processes is always of drinking water quality and not directly from sewage (it will have undergone treatment). However, being the first to successfully introduce a beer made with effluent could potentially lead to high popularity, provided it tastes good.

It is not necessarily a question about quality, but more the public perception of using effluent for certain purposes. A recent study was carried out to investigate whether people are prepared to use water from effluent for other purposes like showering. There is growing understanding and improvement around water reuse.

In systems where water treatment is involved, regulation puts a maximum limit of 10 years for effluent reuse. 10 years is challenging given the investments made compared to getting something useful out of the effluent without having too much of a risk to use it for agriculture or other purposes. Such legislation is possibly for environmental reasons. In Belgium, there are big concerns about PFAS in the water cycle and the spreading of PFAS. While there are measures to address it, it is not always clear where the next source of PFAS will be from or the impact it will have. Environmentalists and/or environmental organisations are therefore cautious. They are keen on using effluent to replenish wetlands and return nature to function the way it should but want to ensure that it is of the right quality so as not to exacerbate existing issues like PFAS contamination.

Recently, Elsevier published a study in November 2022 on the risk perception and social attitudes towards water reuse. The study, titled “Public acceptance of recycled water: A survey of social attitudes toward the consumption of crops grown with treated wastewater”, highlights that while the technology for treating wastewater and ensuring safety is well-established, there remains consumer resistance to accepting and using treated wastewater. Using representative survey data gathered from 300 respondents living in Flanders, the study showed that water conservation behaviour and a sense of environmental group-efficacy positively affect public acceptance. The study also showed that feelings of disgust and fear of contamination are key drivers of consumer resistance to wastewater reuse and potentially override environmental concern (Verhoest *et al.*, 2022).

Justice

Water treatment systems have proven their capabilities. The focus should be more on accountability and insurance rather than justice-related implications.

Nevertheless, the economic justice of compensating those who provide the effluent and the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the final water product are important considerations. Clarity on the ownership of the final product (the water) and whether organizations like Aquafin should compensate those who contribute the water to their treatment plants are additional aspects that need attention. There needs to be a clear governance structure in which responsibilities are defined (e.g., who is providing the quality, who is responsible for the quality, and at what stage in the process), and regulated economic models to alleviate restraints on effluent reuse.

Drivers and measures

While addressing economic models and defining parameters can contribute to increasing acceptance, **climate change will be the primary driver, forcing the need to explore alternative water sources.**

It is perhaps up to the government to lead the charge in taking long-term action. However, involving all relevant stakeholders, including for example industries, water sector stakeholders, etc., is crucial to prevent a top-down approach that may lead to resistance.

COVID-19 and gender related considerations

With respect to the influence COVID-19 might have on the acceptance of effluent reuse, transparency, public awareness, and choice are important. If consumers are informed about effluent reuse in agriculture and the food industry labels products made with reused water, people can make informed decisions. Lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic, such as creating awareness and providing choices, could be applied in this case.

In terms of gender implications, potential concerns related to wastewater residuals, such as medications and chemicals, and their impact on health might be considered. From a gender

perspective, some individuals might have reservations about the health implications of reusing water that contains substances like contraceptives and hormones. However, these concerns are not necessarily exclusive to gender but rather a general concern about the impact it might have on health.

3.4.2.2. Stormwater reuse for agriculture

Building trust with the local farmers as well as citizens who live close to the site where the stormwater basin will be built is very important. Proefstation has strong contacts with local farmers who have been involved in the pilot from the start of the project. Water infiltration will take place on their fields, therefore underpinned information about benefits and/or risks is needed to gain trust. Local citizens had been informed of the B-WaterSmart project by the City of Mechelen with an information letter and a local event that was organised for them in the fall of 2022.

The following sections will provide a synthesis of the findings from the interviews. This section will be partially structured using the conceptual model for social acceptance assessment used in B-WaterSmart.

Risk perceptions and attitudes

The general sentiment observed in Flanders is that most people are supportive of the stormwater reuse recognising the benefit of stormwater reuse, especially as water becomes quite scarce. There is also the impression that **many are very sympathetic with the project to do something for farmers because there is quite a feeling at the moment in Belgium that farmers always have to do more than the rest.**

It is noted that many citizens show little concern or understanding of the potential risks associated with water reuse, e.g., pathogens, even though the risks are small for stormwater reuse. Farmers on the other had have a better understanding and are therefore more conscious of stormwater reuse. **They also realise that the acceptance of stormwater reuse resulting in the introduction of large reservoirs could also attract other types of sectors of the farming industry, increasing the competition for water.**

While environmentalist are not against the use of stormwater for agriculture, there are potential conflicts due to the limited availability of space in the region and the conflicting interests between nature conservation (ensuring sufficient water flow in waterways for ecological purposes) and agricultural needs. Having experienced severe droughts in 2017 and 2018 limiting the availability of water, choices need to be made on the use of available water.

While rainwater is generally considered good quality, there are concerns about pollutants such as microplastics, hydrocarbons and salt from road. This could have potential impacts on groundwater quality. Also, the potential risk of sewage in stormwater resulting from incorrect connections between houses and rainwater pipes, or questions about the quality of water stored at sites where waste from households and industries is stored are likely to raise concerns around the reuse of stormwater.

Another concern raised, relates to the location of big reservoirs storing stormwater. They are built above ground with a particular impact on the landscape. Also, when working with a foil for the water storage with no interaction with groundwater, this will have an ecological impact.

Transportation is another point for concern. While farmers are able to access stormwater from the reservoirs, they need drive to get the water and drive back. This is not ideal for farmers because of the time and energy required. Efficient distribution and easier access to stormwater is something that should be addressed in new projects.

Justice

Farmers are burdened with new regulations and insufficient support (e.g., the nitrogen discussions). The general acceptance of stormwater reuse brings new opportunities to farmers in terms of access to sufficient water of the required quality for their business.

In Flanders, a lot of money goes to urban drainage and to improving the urban system so that rainwater can infiltrate into the ground. There is little value put on rainwater infiltration from farmlands. From a justice standpoint, it would be fair that a farmer gets paid for the water that is infiltrating from his or her field. As such, considering the value of rainwater infiltration from farmlands and the possibility of compensating farmers for their contributions to groundwater recharge is something that could be considered or explored further.

Efforts should be put to ensure clear frameworks for water distribution and pricing to avoid unfair access across stakeholders. It is possible that farmers closer to water storage locations may benefit more from easier access.

Drivers and measures

Regulations on water reuse and the impact of climate change on water availability play a role in driving acceptance of stormwater reuse to meet the water needs of the agricultural sector. In Flanders, there seems to be a growing recognition and sense of responsibility among the food processing industries to support farmers; they need enough product from the farmers. In fact, there are cases where industries are collecting runoff water to supply it to farmers. For industries, investing green and blue initiatives to meet sustainability requirements will greatly contribute to loan prospects in the future.

To promote greater acceptance, effort and resources could be put on the implementation of solutions, and in such a way demonstrate the added value of solutions like stormwater reuse. Looking beyond the B-WaterSmart project, considerations on funding and ownership of solutions for subsequent follow-up should be explored.

Sharing best practice stories, emphasizing the value and benefits of stormwater reuse, focusing on legal and technical aspects, and establishing a governance model for water reuse in Flanders can contribute to its acceptance and adoption.

COVID-19 and gender

There are no COVID-19 or gender related considerations with respect to social acceptance of stormwater reuse for agriculture.

The years of COVID-19 were rather dry years in Flanders. The focus has been on ensuring or securing water supply. There are other food related issues that are more important and have maybe more impact on awareness and social acceptance of certain types of water (e.g., potential for EHEC from reusing treated wastewater).

3.5. Lisbon

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"The [Vira] beer also plays that role, we can demonstrate that we manage to transform wastewater into a good quality water to make beer. You taste it, you like it and you won't get sick because it's very high quality. This will raise citizens' trust in the institutions, the utilities, the regulations and control systems." (interviewee)

The various objectives to be developed within the LL Lisbon are mainly described in deliverable D1.7 (section 6.6) and milestone MS06 (section 3.5). In this regard, the proposed solutions aim to increase efficiency by quantifying the components of the water cycle in the city, create an observatory to raise awareness of water issues, establish a methodology for assessing the risks of using alternative water sources, specifically reclaimed water reuse, develop decision support tools, and finally, create and implement a climate readiness index for buildings.

To access information regarding the acceptance of reclaimed water, an analysis of stakeholders' discussions during the three Community of Practice (CoP) meetings held in the city was conducted, along with two interviews with key individuals involved in water management and governance in Portugal.

Within LL Lisbon, in-depth analysis was conducted on the social acceptance issues related to the implementation to water reuse. The other tools developed within the project were not extensively analysed at this point, as they are digital tools to be used within the Living Labs (LLs) for optimizing water management and demand and we consider they do not have direct implications for acceptance issues. The 'climate-ready' certificates will be the subject of a specific focus group to be held with stakeholders in September 2023, therefore will be under the scope of the next version of this report, D5.7 (M48).

One of the objectives of the three CoP meetings held by LL Lisbon was to discuss the state of social acceptance for the development of water reuse schemes in the city. Additionally, interviews were conducted with a representative from the water services regulator and a representative from the water management and governance support agency, which were the main sources analysed in this document. The interviews covered the elements of the social acceptance model adopted by B-WaterSmart.

Acceptance of the adoption of water reuse in the urban water cycle

In 2019, Portugal implemented comprehensive legislation on the reuse of reclaimed water for non-potable purposes, in line with EU regulations. In addition to this regulatory framework, the Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) developed a guide for the implementation of reuse, providing guidelines for urban areas. These two documents have been instrumental in guiding the implementation of reuse practices in Lisbon.

Lisbon LL aims to implement three pilots where reclaimed water is used for irrigating green spaces in the Lisbon municipality. Since this is still a recent practice for stakeholders and citizen users, issues related to risk perceptions, trust, and fairness, as well as community attitudes, directly influence how the development of this new technology will unfold on the ground.

The analysed information was primarily derived from the latest CoP held on May 10th, 2023, focusing on the following themes: information and communication, governance models, and assessment and monitoring of water reuse. The interviews were conducted individually with active partners of the CoPs. The selection of interviewees was based on their expertise in their respective scopes of action.

The main barriers to social acceptance of treated water reuse were identified, with many of them being common to both interviewees. The notes from the CoP meetings were used to complement the diagnosis. The main challenges and barriers identified are categorised below.

3.5.1. Risk perceptions

Risks to human health

One of the major concerns regarding the social acceptance of reclaimed water reuse is related to public health. The potential risks to human health are a highly relevant factor in determining the social acceptance of reuse practices. Generally, citizens perceive reused water as having inferior quality and potential risks to human and environmental health. The closer the contact with reclaimed water, the lower the acceptance of its use.

Perception of scarcity

The perception of scarcity, which creates a sense of urgency, is also crucial for the social acceptance of reuse. This is because the perception of the risks that water scarcity brings reinforces the urgency of adopting sources that ensure future availability of the resource. In Portugal, there is still a low perception of scarcity due to the country's reasonable water sources for supply. However, this perception has been changing due to various drought episodes the country has faced in recent decades and the challenges brought about by the effects of climate change on the coastal region. III Large Sustainability Survey in Portugal, compared to previous surveys in 2018 there is a raise in concerns with climate change, water scarcity, along forest fires (Schmidt *et al.*, 2022). There is a notable influence of the media attention to these problems, as they were highly mediatized during the application of the survey in the Summer 2022. In addition, other recent surveys demonstrated the high influence of major news organisations, especially TV, along with documentaries, as key sources of information on climate issues (Reuters, 2020)

Possible countermeasures

When it comes to risks to human health and the environment, it is crucial to ensure diligent quality control through monitoring and strong regulation for users, but also that this work is well communicated in a simple yet accurate language, providing the necessary context for the correct interpretation of data. Availability of information and actions that generate awareness that the reclaimed water used in this approach is safe for use are also important. As for the perception of scarcity, it is critical for the public to understand that there is an urgency to introduce new water sources that guarantee future human consumption. For this purpose, participatory methodologies and awareness-raising campaigns are important to increase the necessary sense of urgency to support the implementation of the solution. Initiatives such as the mobile app from ERSAR, the national regulator, are best practices that increase transparency and can be built upon to cover more types of data, raising trust and ownership among citizens and consumers. Products such as 'Vira' beer, that can be perceived as 'light' and 'fun' among specific target groups, allow to showcase potable uses of reclaimed water.

3.5.2. Trust

Transparency and information accessibility

Transparency and easy access to information regarding reuse projects, along with active public participation, engagement, and coordination among different stakeholders, will be crucial in fostering trust among the various actors involved in social acceptance of reuse.

According to the analysed data, there is still an issue regarding the dissemination and availability of consistent data that foster greater public trust in reused water. Despite the requirement for signs indicating the use of reclaimed water, tangible information for the public is still lacking.

Trust between citizen and institutions

Public trust in institutions will be a driving force for the adoption of water reuse. Currently, there is general trust in the water utilities by the public, but this is lower in services with a smaller scale, such as rural areas. Water Transparency Indexes have revealed that for Portugal trust in public institutions has not improved over the last few years.⁶ However, due to stringent EU regulations transposed to national legislation, drinking water is treated to a very high standard. Most of the population consumes tap water and trusts its quality, yet there is a persistent belief among a significant portion of the consumers that tap water lacks quality. In a survey conducted among a representative sample of the national population (Águas de Portugal, 2021), 22% of the respondents declared they did not drink tap water. When it comes to water reuse, trust has not yet been fully established, as this is a recent development in the water management system, still at a pilot stage.

Regarding trust between institutions, Portugal already demonstrates a consistent stage in water management among different parties. However, there are management barriers that hinder the implementation and development of projects, as they require significant collaboration between various institutions to be put into practice. This is also due to the limited experience in water reuse and the lack of a consolidated market. For a more detailed analysis of the water governance system in Portugal, please refer to the B-WaterSmart report D5.5. – Proposal for a New Governance Model.

Possible countermeasures

To address the problem of lack of information and transparency, it is necessary to work on disseminating information and making it more accessible through campaigns and the availability of data that bring water-related issues into discussion. Although citizens already have some awareness of the issues surrounding water, it is still necessary to consolidate this knowledge to minimize the effects of the repulsion factor that citizens may have (known as the 'yuck' factor). A key issue that has been discussed during the most recent CoP meetings is the need to reduce the stigma around the concept of 'waste'. Actions that promote awareness, as well as those that provide assurance of quality and rigorous monitoring of reuse, will be essential in building trust among the stakeholders and citizens. Additionally, fostering new management models that facilitate coordination among different actors is important for enhancing trust between institutions.

3.5.3. Notions of justice

Costs of reuse

The costs associated with reuse are a significant concern among stakeholders in CoPs and the interviewees. Both stakeholders and citizens perceive the costs required for reuse as a barrier to its acceptance. These costs are deemed excessively high, and without financial support, the feasibility of implementing the solution becomes highly unlikely. The expenses are primarily related to infrastructure construction, advanced water treatment, and the need for support to make reclaimed water competitive in a market where access to potable water is relatively inexpensive.

⁶ Index of Transparency in Water Management (INTRAG), 2018 - <https://repositorio.ul.pt/handle/10451/35471>

Currently, Lisbon is investing in the construction of tunnels to transport reused water to different parts of the city, as well as in the production of reclaimed water. However, there is currently no established business model, which hinders interest in the production and commercialization of this water. Additionally, only the Lisbon City Council holds a license for the use of reused water.

Another barrier to implementation is the concern expressed by interviewees regarding additional costs on top of the existing water treatment fees paid by consumers for the production of reclaimed water. They advocate for a user-pays principle, whereby those who use the water bear the associated costs, particularly the industry sector. Future business models will have to ensure a fair distribution of costs and benefits, considering the need for significant investment in infrastructures and eventually transportation in some cases.

Possible countermeasures

Regarding the costs of reuse, it is necessary to promote equal access conditions for everyone. In this sense, it is important to ensure state funding for the required infrastructure and consolidate business models that foster a market, encouraging the adoption of reuse.

3.5.4. Attitudes

The attitudes of citizens towards reuse are viewed positively by the interviewees. They believe that actions such as watering green spaces, when public safety is ensured, are a valid water source for the city. However, a barrier that still exists is the willingness to pay for this use. The willingness to pay for reuse is still low among household consumers and it has not been tested whether they would be available to pay increased tariffs to support a circular economy for water. Also, companies and water utilities will need to regard their future investment in reuse as economically viable (e.g., through long-term provision contracts), especially as there is limited scope for raising tariffs.

For the implementation of the solution and future focal areas of the analysis of social acceptance, the following lessons can be drawn from this analysis regarding suitable measures to secure or increase the acceptance of this solution:

- Safeguarding water quality standards, which have been established in Portugal through recent legislation that regulates the licensing of users.
- Ensuring the availability of qualified professionals to manage large-scale treatment plants for the production of reclaimed water within the necessary quality parameters.
- Guaranteeing the clear and transparent dissemination of information regarding the quality of reclaimed water.
- Bringing the importance of awareness-raising actions to increase the understanding of water scarcity and, consequently, the sense of urgency among citizens and stakeholders.
- Promoting actions of articulation between institutions through new governance and management models that involve the stakeholders in the sector with the aim of fostering trust among all parties involved.
- Ensuring fair access for citizens through financial incentives.
- Developing business models that support the water reuse schemes.
- Eventually in the future prohibiting certain uses of potable water and allowing only the use of reclaimed water (incentives through restrictions), e.g., for watering golf courses and green spaces.
- Optimising the licensing processes to expand the scope of reuse projects.
- Promoting stronger and more inclusive public participation in decision-making processes.

3.6. Venice

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3.6.1. Key issues of social acceptance

The main implications for acceptance of water-smart solutions in LL Venice relate to two dimensions:

- the urban reuse of effluent, although this is not the main type of reuse, so it is far from the need to measure its social acceptability;
- the application in agriculture of sewage sludge: farmers as “end-users” enabled/protected by the respective trade associations, which, together with the regulatory authorities of the sector, have an important role in the acceptance of any innovative solutions for water reuse and sludge management.

Therefore, in the discussion below we focus on the various categories of stakeholders, highlighting the reasons for any resistance, that in short are the barriers we try to address precisely with the solutions implemented in the case study as extensively discussed in the previous table. Citizens will be approached and treated in a subsequent phase (at the end of the PILOT phases and the DSSs development), i.e., when it will be possible to demonstrate, with the support of the governance itself, the actual nature of the problems, refuting or starting at least to mitigate the previous beliefs/culture.

In general, no particular resistances by the CoP stakeholders for the BWS solutions put in place by the Venice LL have been identified. On the contrary, there is a high sensitivity on applying reuse and recovery practices of water and related resources. The CoP activity has been quite intense, the stakeholders collaborate in a crosscutting way. There have been several CoP-Focus Group meetings, on several topics (specific barriers, legislations, costs etc.): many of them have been crucial for the DSSs development (solutions - water reuse #16, sludge management #19), for identifying the best variables/data/information to be gathered and the way to intercept. Among the total 36 CoP meetings held until today, 31 have been Focus Groups meetings.

Several are the factors that have triggered this high level of acceptability of solutions proposed in the case study: the main is upstream and it consists in a certain coincidence of intents between us (our case study) and the territorial governance about some fundamental themes such as sludge valorisation and water saving. For an important part of issues treated by the project in fact, our case study was designed to pursue objective and shared needs, at least in terms of intent, by the territory and governance. For this reason, since the start of project developing, we spent a lot of effort in involving the top roles of all the key organisations and institutions in the water supply chain (key stakeholders), to verify in more detail the coincidence of intentions and discuss the development strategies of the case and the attentions to be paid (barriers to overcome).

For each one of the key organisations, including end-users, where they do represent a determinant audience in adopting the B-WaterSmart solutions (such as the industrial end-users, the key-stakeholders for which we held the first focus-CoP meeting, in early 2021), there were several “one-to-one” meetings to share goals and clarify premises, as well as developing a common path.

Once this phase has been overcome (lasted about 6 months) and strategies to be pursued have been shared, the top authorities themselves, or other officials designated by them (with power to decide and actively collaborate), started their collaboration with us, by following a calendar built on the needs foreseen, with changes based on the needs that emerged over time.

Summing up

In relation to **general reuse of effluent** (WR platform, Sol. #16), the social technical component demonstrates high adherence to the scope, all local stakeholders are working to build the conditions for fostering/implementing practices of effluents/water reuse (with several projects put in place also due to the drought events of Summer 2022). All stakeholders are involved, some of them (the civil engineering offices of the Veneto Region, named “Geni Civili”, in charge of granting authorisations for water withdrawals towards all different uses) joined recently the team to collect and make available data required for the development of DSS on water reuse.

Regarding **effluent reuse to industrial uses** (solution #4 to demonstrate its feasibility, towards the nearby industries of Porto Marghera industrial area), the industrial stakeholders (target end-users) and trade associations adhered from the very beginning to the strategic objective set in the strategic agenda, showing high support towards the implementation of the solution and a willingness to test it. Some minor doubts and resistances, expected to be solved with the results of the demonstration phase, are related to the quality of reclaimed water and costs.

Concerning **nitrogen recovery** (solution #11), a specific category of target group (trade associations for farmers) will be involved at a later stage, once the results from the pilot demonstration will be available and the high quality of the recovered product is proven.

Regarding **sludge valorisation** (solution #19), the situation is a little more complex, since for several reasons a certain prejudicial vision is widespread and ingrained. All stakeholders are aware that in this field there is distortion in the perception of quality; there are some fears that this product (though coming from civil WWTPs) can hide risks. This perception relates also to target organisations such as the authority guaranteeing the agricultural application. The DSS under development (#19) is a solution put in place exactly to mitigate/solve these resistances.

3.6.2. Insights from the CoP meetings

The table below summarises all the information relevant for the acceptability of B-WaterSmart solutions, the attitudes per target group and other factors considered by the B-WaterSmart social acceptance model. Each solution of Venice LL has been analysed through the lens of each factor constituting the BWS social acceptance model (e.g., risk perception, fairness notions, etc.) to give a complete overview about the current situation. Information was gathered through investigating each specific solutions during all CoP meetings carried out up to the current evaluation (36 CoP meetings in total, 31 of which are Focus Groups meetings) in which all target groups per each solution were present. As mentioned in section 3.6, the general public does not play a direct role in our case: mainly technical reuse objectives are pursued, for which society and citizens are not directly affected.

Table 5 - B-WaterSmart acceptance model applied to Venice LL solutions

Factor in analysis (BWS model)	General Water Reuse and effluent valorisation (Solution #16)	Industrial Effluent Reuse (Solution #4)	Nitrogen recovery (Solution #11)	Sludge Valorisation (Solution #19)
Risk perceptions	<p>About the way of implementing at national level the EU Reg. 2020/741 on water reuse. If not correctly implemented (roles/responsibilities, cost covering means, not well defined, and excessive quality requirements with respect to the risks): there is the risk that, as previously commented, the practice of effluent reuse is hindered rather than promoted.</p>	<p>Slight risk perceived by the industrial end-users, i.e., the main target group, towards reclaimed water quality especially for microbiological characteristics.</p>	<p>Target groups have not yet been involved, but all other stakeholders agree that a potential risk that could be perceived, is connected to the quality of the recovered product.</p>	<p>Regardless of the causes, the main risk perceived relates to the quality implications of this product.</p>
Fairness notions	<p>High awareness among stakeholders in need to reconcile concomitant uses of freshwater during events of drought. Several solutions are being examined (reservoirs for rainwater collection; various projects for effluent reuse; anti-salt barriers directly into strategic rivers, to avoid the rising salt wedges). The accessibilities to the resource are optimal for all uses. No issues related to fairness notions.</p>	<p>Awareness among the industrial end-users in need to save freshwater. No issues related to notion fairness. No issues related to fairness notions.</p>	<p>No issues related to fairness notions.</p>	<p>Awareness of need to valorise sludge towards the most appropriate direction - some disturbed perception however on quality and risks. Apart from that, no issues related to notion fairness.</p>

Factor in analysis (BWS model)	General Water Reuse and effluent valorisation (Solution #16)	Industrial Effluent Reuse (Solution #4)	Nitrogen recovery (Solution #11)	Sludge Valorisation (Solution #19)
Trust	Trust among the several roles and local authorities; exists a certain concern about the potential incorrectness of the EU Regulation national acquisition.	No issues perceived/to be detected	No issues perceived/to be detected	A low trust by a part of governance on transparency and traceability of sewage sludge management was found; this is under resolution thanks the strategic DSS for sludge valorisation, in developing phase.
Distributive & procedural justice	No issues perceived/to be detected	No issues perceived/to be detected	No issues perceived/to be detected	No issues perceived/to be detected
Attitudes	High level of Intention to adopt	High level of Intention to adopt	Intention to adopt (if the case)	Intention to adopt (if the case)
Acceptability	High level of acceptability	High level of acceptability	High level of acceptability (if the case)	High level of acceptability (if the case)
Socio-political acceptance	Good acceptance at any level of society (technical and public) is expected. It has not been directly assessed, but there are not social concerns or negative discussions towards innovations in this sector and towards this kind of solutions.	Good acceptance at any level of society (technical and public) is expected. It has not been directly assessed, but there are not social concerns or negative discussions towards innovations in this sector and towards this kind of solutions.	Not applicable now at public level.	High support and participation in the developing phase of the DSS which will enable the spread of a fair and transversal knowledge. The public social level is not directly addressed, but, due to information distortion by the media, the social climate and the discussions around the scope of this solution are expected to be,

Factor in analysis (BWS model)	General Water Reuse and effluent valorisation (Solution #16)	Industrial Effluent Reuse (Solution #4)	Nitrogen recovery (Solution #11)	Sludge Valorisation (Solution #19)
				though indirectly, negatively affected.
Market acceptance	Theoretical positive acceptance of a (potential) market (though a real market is difficult to be seen) - provided that roles and responsibilities and cost coverage are identified correctly and in time.	Theoretical positive acceptance of the market: but the final practical answer will undergo the business models found and put in place, also to not interfere too much the actual Market.	Not applicable now (not still demonstrated the convenience and the implications)	This solution should enable a more equitable and stable sludge management policy by allowing medium-long term strategic planning and by discourage speculation and by stabilizing management costs. In such a perspective, all stakeholders agree on the economical convenience of this solution (also for the market).
Community acceptance	Not yet investigated, since not relevant now (the social dimension is not involved nor affected directly). In the future, if the case, community acceptance will be taken into account, and awareness raising goals will be pursued with training, specific educational/information campaigns, mediated by social media, public meetings etc...			

4. Conclusions and next steps

In this last section, selected elements of the acceptance model were analysed against the key solutions in development in the B-WaterSmart Living Labs, in order to identify the most critical issues to be addressed over the next year of the project, towards the final version of this report in Month 48 (D5.7). Table 6 summarises the key issues.

Table 6 - Summary of key issues of social acceptance at the B-WaterSmart LLs

LL	Alicante	Bodo	East Frisia	Flanders	Lisbon	Venice
Water reuse & sludge	Infrastructure cost, need for a fair distribution of costs-benefits, agricultural sector may be reluctant to accept this option	Abundance of water resource has not led to need for reuse, but other water challenges at stake	Barriers to re-use of cow water' in food chain (dairy industry)	Potential concerns for reuse of wastewater in food industry (e.g., breweries)	Infrastructure cost, need for a fair distribution of costs-benefits	Costs and quality possibly issues to be addressed during demonstration phase, especially for sludge
Stormwater management		Need to improve literacy on the water systems (climate change and NBS)		Ensure clear frameworks for water distribution and pricing to avoid unfair access across stakeholders; possible trade-offs/conflicts between nature conservation and agriculture.		
Digitalisation/ smart meters	Digitalisation offers a good opportunity for consumption monitoring and implementation of incentives for responsible consumption, such as providing additional water for every cubic meter saved.	Privacy concerns over data used for smart meters	Privacy concerns over data used for smart meters			

4.1. Risk perceptions

One of the key approaches followed in B-WaterSmart is the treatment of wastewater or process water for reuse, for potable and non-potable uses. Hygienic risks certainly play a role as a barrier in public perception (e.g., East Frisia). The perception of reclaimed water as 'waste' may constitute a barrier for acceptability for use in the food chain (interviews EF, CoP Lisbon), as people tend to associate process water with a waste product, in particular if the origin, treatment and safety measures are not properly explained. If this is to be consumed via the food chain, there is a different psychological barrier to be overcome than in the case of recycling/reuse of waste or by-products into other consumer products (East Frisia). Breweries may also avoid using reused water in processes where there could be potential contact with their product. The public perception of using effluent in food and beverage production is a potential barrier/concern (also relevant for Flanders). Nevertheless, landmark products such as Vira beer can have a positive marketing impact on a wider acceptance of water reuse among younger groups (Lisbon).

The interviewees have highlighted the importance of carrying out visual experiments and informative events to address these concerns and promote a 'circular' culture of reuse (especially relevant for farmers in Alicante). Survey data gathered from 300 respondents living in Flanders showed that feelings of disgust and fear of contamination are key drivers of consumer resistance to water reuse and potentially override environmental concern (Verhoest et al., 2022). Active community participation and word of mouth were identified as effective ways to influence social acceptance. Government institutions and the media were deemed important for promoting and ensuring the acceptance of reclaimed water through campaigns and necessary safety controls.

While B-WaterSmart was already under development, other challenges related to pressing need for climate change adaptation, beyond water scarcity, imposed themselves on the policy agenda. Intergenerational justice plays a role here through the idea of sustainability: water-smart solutions contribute to the protection and more sustainable management of the water resources, and thus ensures intergenerational justice (East Frisia).

In a context where there has been a surge in tourism and real estate across the EU member-states, especially as they face a long-standing socio-economic crisis, it is timely to interrogate how this profound shift in the housing and property market is going to concur to the effort of climate adaptation, alongside the Paris Agreement, the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, and the Green Deal. At the very least, there should be sustainability requirements for new property development, as there were for certain developing countries that went through an increasing demand of tourism foreign investment.

Historically the areas with more abundant water resources have been less concerned with measuring water consumption (Bodø), but future challenges may bring about a shift in the paradigm for water management in urban areas, especially as new estate developments prop up. Even in Southern Europe, historically most affected by recurrent droughts and threatened by water scarcity, there is still a lack of awareness among the general public regarding the urgency of the water challenges, although this perception is gradually shifting, with more recurrent and serious droughts over the last few years (Lisbon). Future water challenges will push for smart metering and also demand forecasting such as the tools under development

in East Frisia LL (#28). There will be necessarily economic consequences to the deployment of such tools, leading to a new price structure.

The Bodø Living Lab followed suit by integrating this debate within the CoPs. As this LL is working in a new development area (from where the airport was dislocated), the discussion on how to integrate nature-based solutions into the urban water cycle prompted up. Currently there is a debate in Norway on municipalities' right or not to require nature-based solutions on private land, and the question of who should then pay, the developer or the municipality, for blue-green infrastructures. Some of the statements in the CoP workshop suggest that it is easier for larger developers to find ways around requirements and requests in this area, than for smaller developers. As such, there could be potential challenges related to justice between small and large developers, if the small ones are burdened by additional costs for NBS.

One of the key insights from debates within the CoPs and interviews across many LLs is that there is generally a low literacy on the water challenges and the water cycle, which is crucial for community acceptance of innovative solutions. Other risks related to the impacts of climate change on the water cycle are still poorly understood by citizens, which may impact the willingness to invest in more sophisticated solutions, such as NBS for stormwater management in Bodø. Floods and heavy rains have become more frequent and intense, requiring an overall reorganisation of the water management system, starting with storage capacity in cities.

Municipalities play a crucial role in promoting green spaces for adaptation (e.g., cooling and carbon sequestration). Education, especially in schools, was highlighted as an essential pillar, emphasising practical learning through experiments and small pilots (Alicante), as well as involving property managers in decision-making.

While ensuring quality reclaimed for reuse, there is a need to keep in perspective the synergies and trade-offs along the nexus water-energy-waste. Due to the high technical effort required to produce water of drinking quality from process water, environmental concerns can also constitute a barrier, because this solution may be seen as only shifting the problem: high energy costs for treatment and negative environmental effects if the energy used is not climate neutral.

4.2. Notions of justice

This dimension relates mostly to the acceptance of end-users (stakeholders in industry and agriculture), as some key water-smart solutions require a new scheme for water management, namely the construction of new infrastructures for the provision of alternative sources of water (reclaimed water) that will necessarily imply additional costs. While this will likely be ensured by public funding at an early stage (e.g., the new reclaimed water networks in Lisbon), over the next few years there will be the need for a co-responsibility and share of costs-benefits across the key sectors that will be the target of these new resources, especially industries and agriculture.

The notions of justice and possible conflicts of interest arise mostly in the context of market acceptance, the reason why WP5 has highlighted the need to investigate further the

willingness to pay for these new infrastructures and possibly new water tariffs for these end-users, in the implementation and replication stages of B-WaterSmart solutions (T7.3). It is necessary to assess whether industries with high water consumption might be interested in investing in their own reuse systems or water innovative solutions, which is mostly relevant for LLs Alicante and Lisbon. Transport and infrastructure costs are the main issue at stake for implementing circularity of water reuse in agriculture and rural areas (e.g., replication in Lisbon Metropolitan Area or peripheral areas of Alicante).

Regarding willingness to pay, given the present economic situation there is not much scope to increase tariffs among household consumers. There might be the need to create special tariffs or use restrictions for non-potable uses in drought-prone areas (applicable to all LLs except Bodø), such as golf camps in Portugal. To increase the uptake of reclaimed water, utilities will need to ensure the viability of contracts, namely through long-term contracts that may allow to ensure provision over the year and might require specific regulation.

Efforts should be put in to ensure clear frameworks for water distribution and pricing to avoid unfair access across stakeholders. It is possible that farmers closer to water storage locations may benefit more from easier access (relevant for LL Flanders).

4.3. Trust

Trust in institutions in the water sector varies across countries and LL's contexts raising more concern regarding Portugal (Lisbon) and East Frisia - decreasing trust in governmental key actors and institutions - and less for Norway (Bodø). It is important to convey how the consumer gains control over their consumption, by having access to more precise monitoring, but also how greater security of supply and monitoring ultimately benefit society as a whole. Especially as the socio-economic crisis leaves less room for an increase in tariffs (all the more so in light of the energy price inflation), any further control over consumption that is deemed to affect consumer tariffs has to be communicated with great care and transparency.

Also, water tariffs should be adjusted taking into consideration the increase in the cost of life overall, especially for the most vulnerable groups in society (such as low-income households and larger families). Even if water tariffs are generally low in our LL countries, and not generally considered a critical issue, they still have to be accounted for within household expenses. A deeper understanding of how water is used across sectors (industry, agriculture) is also paramount for a greater sense of fairness and justice among citizens, as is well explained in the chapter on LL East Frisia.

However, the adoption of the GDPR has brought to the fore consumer concerns with data privacy; at the same time, the installation of smart meters has become widespread as a means to monitor consumptions and avoid water waste. This type of solution will likely prove to be challenging in the near future and across the LLs, which calls for a reinforcement of communication strategies that ensure transparency but also highlight the advantages of improving water use efficiency, not only from a local but also a global perspective, also outlining possible economic benefits of the user through the realisation of saving potentials.

Trust cannot be secured solely by increasing the number of figures, data and facts provided: larger amounts of unexplained data are more likely to carry the risk that they will be

misinterpreted. It is therefore important to create trust through transparency in the background and objectives of the measures, explaining: What societal problem do we have? What do we want or need to achieve? Where do we want to go and why? What are we doing in concrete terms?

As noted in section 1, social norms may play a crucial role in willingness to adopt such solutions as water smart meters, along with the perceived environmental benefit. Sustainability is an increasingly accepted norm in the society. In the area of the LL East Frisia, there are environmentally conscious groups in the population, some of whom even admonish that water is too cheap at the moment and therefore the careful use of water as a resource has not been sufficiently promoted. Survey data gathered from 300 respondents living in Flanders showed that water conservation behaviours and a sense of environmental group-efficacy positively affect public acceptance of water reuse (Verhoest et al., 2022).

This reasoning is also relevant for Lisbon climate-ready certificates, as they require regular audits and the voluntary adhesion of households and companies, possibly supported in the near future by ever more precise smart meters. Privacy concerns might hinder the installation of smart meters for water consumption in private households, as has been noted especially for LLs Bodø and East Frisia, but this does not amount to a critical risk for the implementation of these solutions in the B-WaterSmart LLs.

This points to an urgent need to improve communication and awareness-raising across the water cycle - involving all relevant stakeholders, including for example industries, water sector stakeholders, etc. - also on the impacts of climate change on the precipitation patterns and increased intensity of extreme events. There is still an urgent need for a broader understanding, amongst stakeholders as well as citizens, on the phenomena of climate change vs climate variability, e.g., recurrent, and serious droughts vs the cumulative effects on water scarcity over years and decades. This long-term is crucial for policymakers, water utilities and authorities to be able to plan ahead.

There is now a higher awareness of risks and possible crises in the population than, for instance, a decade ago (East Frisia). Support can be expected by those who have directly experienced water scarcity or water shortage situations and public calls to save water (e.g., garden watering bans), or who work in particularly water-intensive sectors where conflicts of use are also present (e.g., agriculture). Environmental protection organisations are also expected to be supportive of this sort of technology.

Many are very sympathetic to the project to do something for farmers because there is quite a feeling at the moment in Belgium that farmers always have to do more than the rest (Flanders). Yet, there are potential conflicts due to the limited availability of space in the region and the conflicting interests between nature conservation (ensuring sufficient water flow in waterways for ecological purposes) and agricultural needs. Having experienced severe droughts in 2017 and 2018 limiting the availability of water, choices need to be made on the use of available water.

4.4. Implications of COVID-19 and gender issues

One of the goals of D5.4 was also to report on the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic and gender issues in the implementation of B-WaterSmart solutions. We have discussed the implications of COVID to water safety among the project partners, as well as possible implications for the solutions under development in the project. We have also sought to have health authorities and organisations involved in our Communities of Practice in order to discuss possible concerns with safety of reclaimed water.

Regarding COVID-19, curiously the experience of the pandemic seemed to have reinforced social trends towards increased sustainability, especially as populations became more aware that basic services (e.g., water and energy provision) are not necessarily a given and might be disrupted in extreme circumstances.

The pandemic has given the starting signal for a higher crisis sensitivity among the population. Resources such as water, electricity, gas, are no longer taken for granted. There is a greater understanding that it makes sense to also look ahead for ways to save and find substitute solutions for these resources. This can be a supporting factor for the acceptance of this solution (East Frisia).

With regard to the pandemic's implication in the implementation of B-WaterSmart, the most noticeable at the first stage were the delays in the commissioning of pilot plants, as well as lack of raw materials and electronic components, which in some cases led to delays over six months.

Regarding those aspects more relevant for social acceptance, COVID-19 emphasized the importance of wastewater-based epidemiology, to foster a sense of trust in water utilities and the safety of water provided to consumers. The pandemics also emphasised the importance of improving digital monitoring of water, and identified weaknesses in emergency procedures that require improvements (Alicante). In the case of Flanders, the years of COVID-19 were rather dry years. The focus has been on ensuring or securing water supply in a context of increased demand between sectors (e.g., agriculture and industry), which emphasise the need for solutions such as water reuse.

In terms of user trust, it has generally remained stable, and measures have been taken to ensure water safety, such as continuous COVID-19 presence analysis, which has contributed to building confidence in the water sector. Greater knowledge of digital solutions and wastewater-based epidemiology has emerged. This has led to a better collaboration and collective trust in the water sector.

Regarding gender issues, gender-sensitive approaches, such as promoting women's involvement, have been highlighted as important for the acceptance of innovative water solutions. In some countries, women have demonstrated a stronger predisposition for pro-environmental behaviours, which may work as an advantage for the implementation of water-smart solutions (Schmidt *et al.*, 2022). We have not identified concerns related to the representativeness of women in CoPs and the water sector in general for our European LLs. Women have in fact been assuming an increasing preponderance in the water management sector, and the B-WaterSmart project itself is an example of this shift.

D5.4 is one of the two key deliverables deriving from task T5.3 on “Social acceptance and behaviour toward water-smart solutions”, first a preliminary report (D5.4) in Month 36, later a final version at the end of the project in Month 48 (D5.7). This is the first public report where we had the opportunity to address the main issues across the LLs in light of the key dimensions identified for the B-WaterSmart acceptance model (socio-political, market and community acceptance).

The next iteration of this report will be submitted at the final stage of the project (M48, August 2024) and will benefit of a more complete pool of information from the CoP meetings and surveys carried out across the LLs. The preliminary review and analysis of D5.4 has already allowed us to identify elements that will require more attention in the next stage of the assessment (e.g., the influence of social norms in pro-environmental behaviours) and that will be considered in the final version of the deliverable (D5.7).

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